

PATHBREAK

Negotiation Game: Global Forces, Local Faces

Decision making on a dam project in the tropical rainforest

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Background information

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Summary

The Pathbreak Negotiation Game: Global Forces, Local Faces is a role-playing strategy game that immerses participants in a fictional yet realistic scenario that highlights the complex challenges of political decision-making through a proposed dam project in the tropical rainforest. The focus is on the ecological, economic, and social impacts of the dam project.

In a negotiation game, all participants are assigned a role which they must then advocate for in a simulated dialogue assembly. By incorporating fictional events, informal rounds, and the media activity, an attempt is made to replicate the dynamics of real negotiations.

The game addresses challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, resource distribution, and poverty. The Pathbreak Negotiation Game was methodically designed based on an extensive examination of various materials concerning the Belo Monte Dam in Brazil and related real conflicts.

The goal of the Pathbreak Negotiation Game is to interactively and practically convey the complexity of decision-making processes, the global dimension in local conflicts, and the influence of different actors, privileges, social resistance, and power hierarchies to the participants. The game is recommended for developing key competencies such as communication, cooperation, critical thinking, and intercultural sensitivity. The Pathbreak Negotiation Game is designed for 13 to 23 participants and is particularly aimed at upper secondary school students and university students from various disciplines in the social and environmental sciences.

Pathbreak Neogitation Game: Global Forces, Local Face is a part of the Pathbreak Game Series (www.pathbreak.eu) developed in the PLANET4B Horizon Europe research project (www.planet4b.eu). The distinctive feature of this negotiation game lies in its inclusion of intersectional dimensions and the focus on the consequences of the negotiation for biodiversity and people. The PLANET4B Horizon Europe research project aims to understand how we can make better decisions for biodiversity and people at individual, community, and institutional levels. It addresses plural values, intersectionality, leverage points, attitudes, norms, behaviour and social learning in transformations for biodiversity decision-making.

Introduction

The negotiation game consists of three negotiation rounds. During these rounds, participants are expected to argue for their assigned role’s interests. They have the opportunity to form alliances with others who share the same interests and to engage in informal discussions with other actors. The negotiation rounds are further interrupted by current events through event cards, which can influence the course of the negotiations. Throughout the day, the press plays a significant role, as they can publish statements, interviews, and critiques on the press wall. All other actors have the opportunity to publish their statements additionally through social media posts.

Table 1: Scope and target group

Recommended number of participants
13 - 23

Target group
Upper secondary school students University students, especially in the fields of political sciences, sociology, economics, environmental sciences and management, international relations and development, geography, ethics, and philosophy.
Duration
Approximately 7 hours

Topic

The Pathbreak Negotiation Game: Global Forces, Local Faces demonstrates a conflict of substantial relevance: in the fictional country of Baloria, the construction of a massive dam is planned. This project would flood large areas of tropical rainforest, affecting the territories of local farmers and the livelihoods of an Indigenous community. At the same time, the successful construction of the dam is a central concern of the current government, which aims to promote economic growth and energy security. Additionally, international companies such as the electric car brand Volt and the agricultural company Agrimax Innovation significantly influence the discussion – both ventures of considerable economic importance. Various actors are involved in this conflict, including representatives from business, politics, media, and civil society. Environmental organisations, in particular, have opposed the dam project and filed a class action lawsuit leading to a dialogue assembly. The overarching goal of this dialogue assembly is to discuss the issues and see if it is possible to come to an agreement that takes the interests of the various actors into account and eventually resolves the conflict.

Relevance and Real-world Connection

Although the negotiation game presents a fictional scenario, it reflects real conflicts. Competing interests between economic development and environmental protection have far-reaching impacts on global issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, resource distribution, and poverty. The negotiation game hence addresses topics of crucial importance for understanding the complex challenges we face as a society.

Among other factors, the destruction of natural habitats and the overuse of resources through such large-scale projects lead to an alarming loss of biodiversity globally (Jaureguiberry et al. 2022; Johnson et al. 2017). This also applies strongly to tropical rainforests, considered the most species-rich ecosystems in the world (Gentry 1992). The loss of habitats through deforestation and land conversion threatens the variety of species and the ecosystem services they provide, such as protection against natural disasters and the provision of clean water and air. Additionally, climate change exacerbates the biodiversity crisis as habitats change faster than many species can adapt. Rising temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events threaten the survival of many sensitive species and lead to shifts in the distribution ranges of plants and animals (Bellard et al. 2012). Both biodiversity loss and changing climate threaten human wellbeing and the most vulnerable societies, communities, and individuals are often affected by the consequences of environmental degradation most severely.

By simulating such a conflict, the game offers an opportunity to understand the impacts of human activities on the environment and to comprehend the complexity of decision-making processes for sustainable solutions. It raises awareness of the urgency of biodiversity and

climate action, empowering participants to actively contribute to shaping a more sustainable future.

Methodology of the Negotiation Game Design

The game design, was in general terms motivated by real cases of dam projects — such as the Belo Monte Dam in Brazil—alongside several other hydropower projects worldwide. The Belo Monte Dam project, aimed at harnessing the hydropower of the Rio Xingu approximately 40 km downstream from Altamira, Brazil, encountered numerous delays due to conflicts and legal proceedings. These issues led to revised plans and a substantial reduction in the initially planned flooded area (Fearnside 2006).

Similarly, the roles within the negotiation were designed to reflect the primary stakeholders involved in real-life cases. In the Belo Monte case, for example, these stakeholders included various business and state actors, such as the state-owned power companies Eletronorte and Eletrobras, the Belo Monte Construction Consortium (CCBM), the Ministry of Mines and Energy (MME), and different construction and consulting firms (e.g., Camargo Corrêa), all of which were crucial to the project's success. Large parts of the funding were provided by BNDES (the Brazilian Development Bank) and government pension funds. Pro-dam advocacy groups included local municipal governments and the *Barrageiros* or “dam builders,” citizens among whom the Belo Monte Dam partly gained a sacred status as the “Holy Grail.” International actors were also heavily involved, providing funding, construction support, and insurance for the project, as well as having vested interests in the energy outcomes, such as the aluminium and alumina industries, particularly from China. Conversely, numerous NGOs and initiatives from people affected by the dam, mainly the population of Altamira and Indigenous groups in the Xingu River basin, formed active anti-dam coalitions. These included Indigenous communities (e.g., Munduruku) with support from NGOs (e.g., Comissão Pró-Índio de São Paulo), regional NGOs (e.g., the Movement of People Affected by Dams (MAB)), and numerous national and international environmental NGOs (e.g., International Rivers Network (IRN), Friends of the Earth—Brazilian Amazonia, Greenpeace). Furthermore, the Catholic Church, national and international celebrities, and various politicians engaged in opposition to the dam. The Ministry of the Environment (MMA) and the Brazilian Institute of the Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA) raised some critical voices, while academic involvement was also notable (e.g., by the Nucleus for High-Level Studies of Amazonia (NAEA) or the State University of Campinas (UNICAMP)) (Fearnside 2006).

Argumentation strategies in the negotiation roles were developed based on media publications of these actors and different academic discourse analyses. For instance, the Greenpeace Brazil report (2016) was the main basis for some arguments based on legal frameworks and international declarations/agreements. However, compared to national political and economic imperatives, such environmental and human rights norms have relatively limited impact in this context (Bratman 2014). The indigenous Kayapó, on the other hand, deployed identity politics in their argumentation to achieve recognitional justice in their struggle against large-scale hydroelectric development in the Brazilian Amazon (Zanotti 2015). Government arguments and legitimization strategies focused primarily on national and regional development, energy needs, and environmental impacts (Bezerra et al. 2014). Over the years, Brazilian political elites and military forces have shaped national perceptions of environmentalism and Indigenous peoples, often portraying them as adversaries to economic progress and obstacles to development (Zhourri 2010). Nonetheless, the government’s legitimization strategies concerning the environmental impacts of Belo Monte were effective,

facilitated by the ambiguous interpretation of sustainability (Atkins 2018). Consequently, environmental licensing and financing decisions have become crucial points within energy decision-making processes (Hochstetler 2011; Atkins 2020) and therefore were also central to this negotiation process.

The economic impact (see Dillon and Fishman 2019), environmental consequences (see de Sousa Júnior and Reid 2010), and the effect of reservoirs on the agricultural sector (see Untied 2005; Bro, Moran, and Calvi 2018) were incorporated based on recent literature to provide a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted implications of dam projects. Among the long-term effects of reservoirs is an enhancement of agricultural productivity by increasing crop water use intensity and expanding the total cropland area. Major water storage facilities also reduce water resources and exacerbate environmental variability (Hansen, Lowe, and Xu 2014). Similarly, the precarious situation of local farmers was closely modelled after the challenges faced by small-scale farmers in Brazil as a marginalized group (see Untied 2005).

Of particular interest to social science research is the Belo Monte case due to the high engagement of civil society actors. Through the perspective of Neo-Gramscian hegemony theory, the Belo Monte dam case can be understood as an ideological action of a historic bloc (consisting of the state and capitalist interests), which deployed the discourse of the green economy while marginalizing and dividing the opposition, thereby enhancing the perceived legitimacy of its initiatives (Bratman 2015). Nevertheless, anti-dam coalitions with strong citizen involvement played a critical role in the Belo Monte project outcome. Despite being ultimately approved, the project faced substantial opposition and significant public engagement, leading to major modifications. Belo Monte took 36 years to develop. In contrast, the massive petroleum reserves in Brazil's "pre-salt" region, for example, faced less opposition and were approved much faster, taking only 17 months (Hochstetler 2011).

The relevance of global connections was highlighted in this negotiation game through the influence of foreign investments and the involvement of foreign companies such as Agrimax Innovations and Volt. Local conflicts in dam development in Brazil are deeply embedded in global economic dynamics as well as international agreements. According to M. da Costa (2010), the internalization of international standards and norms by local actors in sustainable dam development conflicts must be emphasized. In the global discourse, best practice understandings and values are prevalent, not least due to the continuous transit of individuals, which impacts local regulations, discourse, norms, and material outcomes. National social and environmental NGOs are often in close contact with international NGOs, with some international NGOs being directly involved. Foreign financial services are integrated through the Brazilian administration's strategy to attract private foreign capital, as well as the expertise of international financial organizations (such as the World Bank) as they engage in related studies - dynamics that tightly embed the local conflict in global processes.

To conclude, the Belo Monte Dam project exemplifies the complexity of negotiating large-scale infrastructure developments that intersect local, national, and international interests. This case underscores the significance of civil society's role and global norms in shaping sustainable development practices and influencing policy decisions as to be simulated in the negotiation game.

Learning Objectives

Negotiation games are effective teaching and learning methods to convey complex concepts and situations as well as develop practical skills. As interactive learning activity, participants

have the opportunity to simulate real or fictional situations and make strategic decisions in teams. This promotes collaboration and the development of problem-solving skills and can be seen as one way of facilitating experiential learning of democracy.

The advantage of negotiation games lies in their ability to convey complex interrelationships in an accessible and practical way. Through active participation, theoretical concepts come to life, and learning is enhanced through experience and reflection.

In the Pathbreak Negotiation Game: Global Forces, Local Faces, the following competencies are particularly strengthened:

1. Understanding the complexity of decision-making in global contexts:

Participants grasp the complexity and interdependencies of decisions, especially in a complex setting like the dam project in the tropical rainforest, while recognising how local conflicts are influenced by global dynamics.

2. Developing communication, negotiation, and problem-solving skills:

Participants enhance their communication and negotiation skills, enabling them to present their viewpoints clearly, find compromises, and effectively analyse complex problems to make informed decisions.

3. Recognising the role of biodiversity, power dynamics, and social issues:

Participants understand the significance of various economic, political, and civil society actors, including the local population and social resistance, as well as reflect on social injustices, privileges, and power relationships within the context of environmental issues.

4. Fostering empathy, intercultural competence, and collaboration:

Participants cultivate empathy by understanding different perspectives, promote intercultural collaboration, respect cultural differences, and work effectively in teams to achieve shared goals.

The Pathbreak Negotiation Game: Global Forces, Local Faces can be used in various disciplines, including political sciences, sociology, economics, environmental sciences and management, international relations and development, geography, ethics, and philosophy. Thus, the negotiation game can help to investigate complex social, ecological, and political dynamics and familiarise students with interdisciplinary challenges in a practical way.

Scenario

Figure 1: Scenario

Economic Context

The negotiation game takes place in the fictional country of Baloria (Figure 1), one of the largest economies in the world. With a GDP of approximately \$1.95 trillion USD and an average economic growth of around 7.6% over the past five years, Baloria is an emerging country with significant potential. The country’s economy is diverse and dynamic, with a wide range of sectors such as agriculture, industry, and services contributing to its prosperity. Despite these economic advances, a substantial portion of the population still lives in poverty. The Gini index is around 53.3%, showing a high inequality within the country. Poverty is particularly widespread in urban slums and remote rural areas. Marginalised groups often lack adequate access to basic services such as healthcare, education, and housing.

Now the country faces a decision about the construction of a large hydroelectric power plant. The planned hydroelectric plant would be one of the largest of its kind and is set to be built on the Dourado River in the Terra Dourada region, a crucial tributary for the tropical rainforest in Baloria. The major project includes the construction of three reservoirs covering a total area of nearly 5,600 km², with the last reservoir featuring a dam with a height of 92 m. The power plant is expected to generate about 12,000 megawatts of hydroelectric power, with construction costs estimated at approximately 13 billion USD.

Political and Economic Consequences

The expected direct and indirect jobs amount to about 41,700 positions. The government of Baloria sees the hydroelectric project as a key initiative to strengthen the country’s infrastructure and energy supply, as well as a driver for economic growth. As potentially the third-largest dam in the world, it would also be a national symbol and attraction. The project aims to enhance infrastructure and provide incentives for other companies to invest in the country.

One such company is Volt, a manufacturer of luxury electric cars, positioning itself as a green company producing electric vehicles to move away from fossil fuels. The cars are in a high price range, affordable only to a few, mostly in the global north. Volt plans to build a Gigafactory in the small town of Maravilha do Norte, about 450 km from the planned dam. For Volt, it is essential that the corresponding infrastructure, including reliable energy supply from the dam, is established in Baloria first. The construction of the Gigafactory would cost another 10 billion USD and create thousands of jobs. Additionally, the large company Agrimax Innovations plans to buy vast agricultural areas in the region due to the dam. The reservoir could enhance approximately 31 irrigation systems for about 580,000 hectares of agricultural land. This makes the area an attractive region for Agrimax Innovations for cultivating soybeans, corn, sugarcane, and cotton.

The operator of the hydroelectric plant and dams would be EnergyGrid Solutions, the largest energy provider in the country. For financing, the operator and investors have formed the EnergyGrid Alliance consortium. The consortium includes various state and private companies as well as Balorian pension funds, with 47.9% of the shares owned by EnergyGrid Solutions.

Environmental Impact and Social Consequences

The environmental impacts would be massive, with an area of 630 km² of tropical rainforest being flooded. This would result in a severe loss of biodiversity of global significance – with the Balorian biodiversity constituting 20% of the total biodiversity of the planet. Changes in the largest tropical rainforest of the earth would also lead to altered water levels and flows that in turn would affect fish migration routes, endangering fish stocks critical to global biodiversity. These ecological changes would have long-term effects on the entire river ecosystem and its surroundings in the tropical rainforest.

Additionally, the river flow would need to be temporarily interrupted for seven months. This would lead to water shortages in the downstream areas of the river, drastically affecting the livelihood of the Indigenous Comnara communities living there. For them, the river is an essential source of food, orientation, and a part of their cultural identity. The extinction of fish species and the artificial interventions in water levels will permanently impact their livelihood, which cannot be restored even after the reservoirs are filled.

Many smallholder farming families in the Terra Dourada region, who traditionally cultivate cassava, sorghum, and beans, would also be affected by the dam. Parts of their agricultural land would be completely flooded by the reservoirs, and compensation and relocation measures would need to be found. It is estimated that in addition to the Comnara around 20,000 people would have to be relocated. Small farmers in the region would have difficulty competing with Agrimax Innovations and would also have to move.

Legal Framework and Dialogue Assembly

The legal situation surrounding the planned dam project is highly complex and multifaceted. Land use rights fall under the responsibility of the President of Baloria and are subject to certain restrictions. According to Article 31 of the national law of Baloria, the government is required to conduct environmental impact assessments and obtain permits to ensure that the dam project meets certain environmental standards. These permits have mostly been granted already by the Ministry of Environment but under specific conditions. These include consultation with Indigenous communities, solutions for relocation compensation,

consultation with local small farmers with adequate compensation for loss of livelihood sources, and the establishment of specific construction times and conditions.

The Indigenous communities in the rainforest area also possess traditional land rights protected by international agreements and national laws. The government must ensure that the interests and rights of these communities are respected and considered. According to international standards such as the ILO Convention 169, Indigenous communities must be included in the decision-making process and give their consent before the project proceeds. Based on these legal frameworks, there has now been a class action lawsuit filed by various NGOs and other civil society actors. In response to this lawsuit, a dialogue assembly has been convened, where all involved parties hope for a goal-oriented dialogue to find a possible compromise.

Gameplay Instructions

Preparation

When inviting participants, make a particular effort to include women and individuals from groups that are often underrepresented in political negotiations. For the preparation of the game, all roles should be assigned at least one day (ideally one week) before the game. It is recommended to allocate all roles randomly, except for the negotiation facilitators, as they should be particularly motivated to manage the discussion and know the game well. Participants should also have access to the scenario and the introduction.

Key materials:

- Scenario and background information (everyone)
- Schedule (everyone, but especially facilitators should be familiar with it)
- Role description (each participant receives an individual role description)
- Event cards (the instructors hold them and decide to use depending on the game flow via the facilitators or journalists)

For the game's progress, it is essential that participants do not get to know the content of the event cards beforehand, and the contents of the other roles should remain concealed as well. Additionally, at least one suitable room ideally with a large round table is necessary, possibly with the option for participants to disperse into other rooms or corridors during the informal round.

The following materials are also needed:

- Printed name tags from the game materials (for all attendees). The name tags should be placed on the tables before the start of the assembly to assign seats.
- Paper and pens for notes; as well as tape or safety pins to attach the name tags.
- Buffet: There will be a lunch break during which important informal discussions can take place. The lunch break can optionally be organised as a potluck buffet.
- Projector
- The PowerPoint presentations included in the game materials for Agrimax Innovations, Volt, EcoVision Global, and EnergyGrid (Solutions and Alliance) should be provided to the participants representing these roles prior to the game. These presentations can be used during the first introduction round.
- Online pad: an online Pad (e.g. in "Pad Systemli" or "Riseup Pad") should be prepared to offer the possibility to quickly and without registration publish a document in which all participants can write using the link. This will serve as a preplace for press releases throughout the game and will be used by journalists for articles and news announcements, as well as by all participants for social media posts. It is therefore recommended to share the link with everyone to enable individual posting, and to set up a laptop with the ability to post if the participants are not using their own. The pad should be permanently projected on the wall via a projector, so new posts can always be read simultaneously.
- Optionally, a flip chart can be provided for participants to illustrate their positions or compromises graphically.
- Schedule: if possible, the schedule should be printed out and posted in the room for review.

Schedule

The game facilitators will have to keep the time which would often mean interrupting the course of the negotiations by announcing the beginning of a new phase. The duration of each phase can be individually adjusted.

Table 2: Schedule

Duration	Phase	Description
15 min	Opening of the Dialogue Assembly	The negotiation facilitators welcome all participants to the dialogue assembly and introduce the context (status of the project, key questions) and agenda.
15 min	Preparation for Introduction Round	All participants have the opportunity to formulate an opening statement (maximum of 3 minutes) for the introduction round. They should briefly introduce themselves and succinctly state their position about the dam construction (support/oppose and why). Alliances can already be formed, and the opening statement can be presented together in a newly formed alliance, if mentioned in the role descriptions.
3 min per statement	Introduction Round	All roles or alliances present their opening statements. Tip: Taking notes on the positions of the other actors or alliances can help discuss each other's positions later.
60 min	First Negotiation Round	After the opening statements, the first negotiation round begins. Try to bring your goals into the discussion and find starting points for compromises.
45 min	Informal Round / Lunch Break	During the lunch break, you can exchange ideas with other negotiation participants and use the pad to strategically post your own social media posts. Press talks as well as bilateral talks to build alliances and develop strategies are also possible. <i>Important:</i> The next negotiation round begins with the opportunity to present a compromise proposal for all roles or alliances within 3 minutes and should be prepared as well.
5 min per press association	Flash News	Before the opening of the second round of negotiations, both press associations have the opportunity to present the latest news in a brief live broadcast.
60 min	Second Negotiation Round	This negotiation round begins with the opportunity to present a compromise proposal for roles or alliances within 3 minutes. These can then be discussed. The pad is always open for posts.
15 min	Alliance Meeting	With potential alliances, you now have one last chance to develop a strategy and work out a compromise. <i>Important:</i> The next negotiation round begins again with the opportunity to present a compromise proposal for all roles or alliances within 3 minutes and should be prepared as well.
5 min per press association	Flash News	Before the opening of the final round of negotiations, both press associations have the opportunity to present the latest news in a brief live broadcast again.
60 min	Final Negotiation Round	This is the last chance to find a solution to the conflict. Give it your all! At the beginning, you again optionally have 3 minutes to present a compromise as an alliance or in your role.
20 min	News Broadcast	The dialogue assembly is concluded. The press issues a news broadcast explaining whether there is a consensus on the dam construction, and if so, under what terms and with which concerns.
15 min	Break	The participants no longer play their roles.
30 min	Debriefing and Evaluation	Outside the roles, the course of the dialogue assembly can now be evaluated. The negotiation facilitator can ask guiding debriefing questions.

Role Distribution

Depending on the number of participants, different role allocations are possible for the dialogue assembly. It is advisable to distribute the roles at least one day (ideally one week) in advance to give participants enough time to prepare for their respective roles. The following table recommends role allocation based on the number of participants.

Table 3: Role distribution

Roles:	Number of participants										
	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
Negotiation facilitator	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Equality officer				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
First Secretary to the President	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Minister of Economy						X	X	X	X	X	X
Minister of Environment	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
City Mayor	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Volt			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Farmers' Association	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Local Fisher		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Agrimax Innovations	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EnergyGrid Solutions	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EnergyGrid Alliance	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Global Development Bank										X	X
EcoVision Global: Policy Advisor	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EcoVision Global: Public Relation Officer					X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Sustainability Network: Project Manager	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Sustainability Network: Policy Advisor							X	X	X	X	X
Comnara: Educator											X
Comnara: Mediator	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newspaper "The Daily Standard": Journalist	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newspaper "The Daily Standard": Editor-in-Chief								X	X	X	X
Press Collective "Unity Dispatch": Journalist	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press Collective "Unity Dispatch": Online Editor									X	X	X

Role Descriptions

Negotiation Facilitator

Who you are

As the negotiation facilitator, you are responsible for the organisation and management of the dialogue assembly. Your role is to ensure the good course of the negotiations, introduce the participants, and adhere to the schedule. This dialogue assembly is part of the legal process triggered by the lawsuit filed by the project opponents. You feel honoured to lead this important event and hope for the full success of the negotiations. In your view, a successful negotiation results in a consensus or agreement with clearly defined key conditions, reached through the inclusive participation of all present stakeholders.

Tasks for opening the dialogue assembly

Once all participants have taken their seats and all materials are prepared as mentioned in the preparation chapter, you will open the event with some welcoming words. You can briefly introduce the conflict according to the scenario description and discuss the presence of such conflicts worldwide. Additionally, you have the task of introducing the participants to the process of the dialogue assembly. Address the following aspects:

Materials:

- Explain the use of the pad. The press will use it for press releases, and all participants can strategically use it for social media posts at any time. Inform the participants that above each post, the name of the person, their position, and the time should be noted.
- The flip chart can also be used at any time to illustrate arguments and compromises.
- The schedule is posted for everyone to see.

Schedule of the Dialogue Assembly:

- Mention that journalists will accompany this event today with interviews and reports.

Briefly present the schedule: There will be a total of three negotiation rounds, as well as informal rounds, flash news and a lunch break. Finally, there will be a news broadcast. Transition to the next event: the dialogue assembly begins with the preparation of the opening statements. All participants now have 15 minutes to formulate a clear position alone or in suitable alliances to present their goals in a maximum of three minutes. Explain that if their position would be strengthened through strategic cooperation with other roles pursuing similar goals, they can approach these partners and form alliances.

Tasks during the dialogue assembly

- Pay attention to the information in the scenario and ensure key facts are not forgotten.
- Foster a positive discussion culture where all participants have the opportunity to speak, and speaking time is distributed as evenly as possible. Use informal rounds to strategize on this. You are permitted to intervene with those who threaten others or monopolise speaking time, yet ideally you should do it diplomatically.

- Adhere to the schedule. Especially during the introduction rounds of the opening statements or compromises, the maximum duration of three minutes per role/alliance should not be exceeded. Intervene accordingly if necessary. Use the schedule to guide participants through the phases of the dialogue assembly and moderate the current task/phase.
- Ensure that the negotiations are goal-oriented. By the end of the dialogue assembly, it should be clear whether the dam will be built or not, or what changes are being sought. This includes what conditions or compensation payments need to be fulfilled or not. Possible compromises to the conflict include compensation from companies in the form of money or land for the affected nature and people, as well as modifications to the overall flooded area or the dam's construction. Other solutions could involve social benefits, alternative energy sources, or energy reduction.
- *Important:* It is also your task to draw an event card at least once an hour (regardless of the current phase). Depending on the event card, you can pass the formulated task directly to the press or carry it out yourself.
- If the discussion stalls, you have the option to draw an additional event card.

As the negotiation facilitator, you have the option, if necessary, to make changes to the schedule according to the negotiation progress. You have the freedom to adapt all aspects according to the current requirements of the game. Thanks to you, this dialogue assembly can take place. You are known for your excellent management and diplomatic skills and will master this task well.

Guiding questions for the final debriefing and evaluation

After the conclusion of the dialogue assembly, participants can express their experiences and thoughts independently of their role. The following guiding questions can help you facilitate the debriefing and evaluation:

- How did you feel during the game?
- What did you notice in the search for a compromise?
- How did you perceive the discussion culture?
- To what extent are you personally satisfied with the result of the dialogue assembly?
- What parallels can you see between this game and reality?
- Which roles could you easily empathise with? / Which roles less so?
- Which value orientations are in conflict here? Where do these value orientations come from?
- Imagine alternative scenarios:
 - How might your character have acted differently if key rules, priorities, or power dynamics were different?
 - What kinds of changes could lead to better outcomes for both people and the environment?

Equality Officer

Who you are

As the equality officer, you help the negotiation facilitator with the organisation and management of the dialogue assembly but with a special focus on creating a non-discriminatory environment. You place great emphasis on ensuring that all participants, regardless of their origin, appearance, gender, religion, or class, have the opportunity to speak, and that a balanced distribution of speaking time is achieved. Together with the negotiation facilitator, your role is to ensure the good course of the negotiations, introduce the participants, and adhere to the schedule. This dialogue assembly is part of the legal process triggered by the lawsuit filed by the project opponents and you are motivated to contribute to a successful outcome of the negotiations.

Tasks for opening the dialogue assembly

The negotiation facilitator has the same tasks as you. Therefore, agree with this person on who will take on which tasks. Once all participants have taken their seats and all materials are prepared as mentioned in the preparation chapter, you will open the event with some welcoming words. You can briefly introduce the conflict according to the scenario description and discuss the presence of such conflicts worldwide. Additionally, you have the task of introducing the participants to the process of the dialogue assembly. Address the following aspects:

Materials:

- Explain the use of the pad. The press will use it for press releases, and all participants can strategically use it for social media posts at any time. Inform the participants that above each post, the name of the person, their position, and the time should be noted.
- The flip chart can also be used at any time to illustrate arguments and compromises.
- The schedule is posted for everyone to see.

Schedule of the Dialogue Assembly:

- Mention that journalists will accompany this event today with interviews and reports.
- Briefly present the schedule: There will be a total of three negotiation rounds, as well as informal rounds, flash news and a lunch break. Finally, there will be a news broadcast.
- Transition to the next event: the dialogue assembly begins with the preparation of the opening statements. All participants now have 15 minutes to formulate a clear position alone or in suitable alliances with allies to present their goals in a maximum of three minutes. Explain that if their position would be strengthened through strategic cooperation with other roles pursuing similar goals, they can approach these partners and form alliances.

Tasks during the dialogue assembly

- Pay attention to the information in the scenario and ensure key facts are not forgotten.
- Foster a positive discussion culture where all participants have the opportunity to speak, and speaking time is distributed as evenly as possible. Use informal rounds to

strategize on this. You are permitted to intervene with those who threaten others or monopolise speaking time, yet ideally you should do it diplomatically

- Adhere to the schedule. Especially during the introduction rounds of the opening statements or compromises, the maximum duration of three minutes per role/alliance should not be exceeded. Intervene accordingly if necessary. Use the schedule to guide participants through the phases of the dialogue assembly and moderate the current task/phase.
- Ensure that the negotiations are goal-oriented. By the end of the dialogue assembly, it should be clear whether the dam will be built or not, or what changes are being sought. This includes what conditions or compensation payments need to be fulfilled or not. Possible compromises to the conflict include compensation from companies in the form of money or land for the affected nature and people, as well as modifications to the overall flooded area or the dam's construction. Other solutions could involve social benefits, alternative energy sources, or energy reduction.
- *Important:* It is also your task to draw an event card at least once an hour (regardless of the current phase). Depending on the event card, you can pass the formulated task directly to the press or carry it out yourself.
- If the discussion stalls, you have the option to draw an additional event card.

Guiding questions for the final debriefing and evaluation

After the conclusion of the dialogue assembly, participants can express their experiences and thoughts independently of their role. The following guiding questions can help you facilitate the debriefing and evaluation:

- How did you feel during the game?
- What did you notice in the search for a compromise?
- How did you perceive the discussion culture?
- To what extent are you personally satisfied with the result of the dialogue assembly?
- What parallels can you see between this game and reality?
- Which roles could you easily empathise with? / Which roles less so?
- Which value orientations are in conflict here? Where do these value orientations come from?
- Imagine alternative scenarios:
 - How might your character have acted differently if key rules, priorities, or power dynamics were different?
 - What kinds of changes could lead to better outcomes for both people and the environment?

First Secretary to the President

Who you are

As the First Secretary of Baloria, you represent a liberal policy focused on modernization and economic growth on behalf of the President. You view the establishment of Volt and the expansion of Agrimax Innovations as essential, making the construction of the hydroelectric power plant indispensable. You know the President's political goals very well and feel confident in representing him in important matters. Your vision aligns with his: creating a dynamic and diverse economy that benefits all citizens. Despite the promising economic situation of the country, you are faced with the challenge of combating poverty in Baloria, which you and the President believe is due to the conservative economic policies of previous governments. After political setbacks in the past, you have worked closely with the Minister of the Economy and the President to develop the "Programme for Accelerated Growth" to attract investments and stimulate the economy. While you feel empowered to make decisions, in critical situations you may decide that more time is needed to consult with the President before reaching a final decision.

For a more authoritative appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may choose to wear a professional suit with a white shirt or blouse. While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

You are convinced of the importance of the companies Volt, Agrimax Innovations, and Energy Grid Solutions for Baloria, and thus also of the planned hydroelectric power plant. You see these projects as an opportunity to boost economic growth and create new jobs, which is of utmost priority for the administration and crucial for the President's reputation and political standing. You argue that an economic upswing for the entire country would also mean an upswing for the municipality, and local stakeholders must make sacrifices for this. You always emphasise the potential economic benefits for the entire country and try to allay the concerns of the opponents of the project with the promise of jobs and prosperity.

Given that the state budget is once again deeply in deficit this year, you do not want the government to bear the costs of potential compensations alone. At the same time, you worry about losing investors if the costs are passed on to the companies involved, particularly Energy Grid Solutions. Therefore, it would be best to keep compensation payments for the environment and potential relocation costs for the affected Indigenous communities as low as possible. Otherwise, you believe that the local municipality Terra Dourada should bear a significant portion of the potential compensation and relocation costs as it will later benefit significantly from business tax revenue. You are annoyed by the lawsuit filed by the project opponents and wish they would propose alternative suggestions for economic growth instead.

Your opportunities

As the First Secretary, you have relatively strong decision-making powers and can offer tax incentives to foreign companies to promote investments, always in alignment with the President's policies. As the President holds the land rights for the area to be leased, including the tropical rainforest and the lands of the local farming families for the dam, you act as his

trusted representative in managing these areas. However, due to legal requirements, you must consult the affected people before leasing the land and obtain the necessary approvals from the Ministry of the Environment. To make the project successful, you are willing to accept low lease rates for the operator EnergyGrid Solutions. Despite limited financial resources, you are committed to advancing the project and are prepared to make compromises to achieve this. Together with the President and the Minister of the Economy, you have also negotiated a secret deal with Volt, which provides for tax-free exports for the company in the first two years. Although you stand behind this deal, it should not become public knowledge, as both your reputation and the President's are at stake!

Your Relationships

You maintain close relationships with the management of Volt and Agrimax Innovations, as well as the officials of EnergyGrid Solutions and EnergyGrid Alliance. Since EnergyGrid Solutions owe their position to the administration, you expect concessions from them in further compromises.

Representing Baloria's interests on the international stage is particularly important to you, and you enjoy speaking with the press and using all opportunities to position Baloria as an attractive business location. However, to avoid bringing unpleasant conflicts too much into the public eye, you strategically avoid direct press interviews with project opponents. Your diplomatic skills and persuasiveness make you a key player in Baloria's political and economic landscape. While you have the trust of the President to make decisions independently, you may choose to consult with him on particularly critical matters to ensure his vision is fully upheld.

Minister of the Economy

Who you are

As the Minister of the Economy for the ruling party in Baloria, you support the First Secretary to the President in this negotiation in all matters, sharing the same goals and capabilities. You are new to this position and are striving to fulfil its demands with full commitment, not least because you appreciate the social status it confers. With the support of the President and the President's First Secretary, you have developed the "Programme for Accelerated Growth," one of your most significant achievements in your political career. With a background in economics, you focus on stabilising the economy through stimulus packages, financial sector support, and promote market participation, aiming to mitigate the adverse effects of the current economic situation on citizens, particularly businesses.

For a more authoritative appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a professional suit or blazer, enhanced by accessories such as ties or subtle pins. While optional, this attire can project confidence and reinforce your presence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

You are dedicated to the success of Volt, Agrimax Innovations, and Energy Grid Solutions, and consequently, to the planned hydroelectric power plant. You view these initiatives as crucial for stimulating economic growth and creating jobs, which are essential for your reputation and political standing.

You are a strong advocate of a free market economy, where minimal government intervention allows the market to operate efficiently. Your policy supports allowing supply and demand to determine prices and enabling companies to function with considerable independence. The dam project, in your view, represents the outcome of fair competition, demonstrating that it is the most viable solution under the current economic conditions. You fully support the project, advocating for tax cuts and reduced bureaucracy to benefit all participating companies. Like the President, you hold the perspective that for national economic growth, some local stakeholders must make necessary sacrifices. You also aim to reassure opponents of the project by highlighting the long-term benefits of job creation and prosperity.

With the state's budget in deficit, you seek to avoid shouldering the costs of potential compensations alone. Concerned about deterring investors, particularly Energy Grid Solutions, you aim to minimise compensation payments for environmental impact and relocation costs for indigenous communities. You argue that the local municipality, Terra Dourada, should bear a substantial portion of these costs, given the future benefits from business tax revenues.

Your opportunities

As the Minister of the Economy, you play a crucial role in shaping national economic policies, including fiscal policy, monetary policy, and regulatory frameworks. You have the opportunity to prioritise funding for different sectors and to set tax rates that impact income distribution, business investment, and consumer spending. However, you generally advocate for tax incentives to attract foreign investments. As a member of the strongest party, and working in alignment with the President's policies, you can reasonably expect that many of your measures will gain the approval of Parliament.

Your limited financial resources do not deter you from advancing the project; you are prepared to make necessary compromises. Together with the President and the President's First Secretary, you have also negotiated a secret deal with Volt, which provides for tax-free exports for the company in the first two years. Although you stand behind this deal, it should not become public knowledge, as your reputation is at stake!

Your Relationships

You maintain strong connections with the leadership of Volt, Agrimax Innovations, and officials from Energy Grid Solutions and Energy Grid Alliance. Given your instrumental role in their success, you expect them to make concessions in ongoing negotiations.

Promoting Baloria's economic interests internationally is a priority, and you actively engage with the press to position Baloria as an attractive business hub. You avoid direct confrontations with project opponents in the media to keep conflicts out of the spotlight. Your diplomatic skills and persuasive abilities make you a crucial figure in Baloria's political and economic landscape.

Ministry of the Environment

Who you are

As the Minister of the Environment, you are deeply rooted in the President's party line while also striving to halt deforestation in the tropical rainforest caused by illegal logging, mining, and agriculture, and to protect the environment overall. Personally, you have remote links in your family to the Indigenous community, which makes you feel sympathy for some of their struggles more than others. You work closely with the team at the Institute for Environment and Renewable Resources of Baloria. This administrative arm of the Ministry of the Environment is responsible for issuing permits that involve interventions in sensitive ecosystems.

The environmental impact assessment commissioned by EnergyGrid Alliance served as the basis for thorough reviews required to grant the necessary permits for the dam project. So far, you have already approved several permits for the dam project, including those for the construction of the hydroelectric plant itself, as well as the roads and power lines leading to it. The permits for the three reservoirs are also in the final stages and are about to be granted. Only specific conditions regarding the restoration of riverbanks, the re-establishment of wetlands downstream, and the purchase of 200 km² of compensatory land are still being discussed. These compensatory lands are to be reforested to partially offset the deforested area.

For a more authoritative appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a professional suit or blazer, enhanced by accessories such as ties or subtle pins. While optional, this attire can project confidence and reinforce your presence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

As the Minister of the Environment, you aim to protect the environment while acknowledging the necessity of the dam and thus primarily trying to support the government's plans with your opportunities. Your main goal is therefore to advance this dam project as sustainably as possible. The less damage to the rainforest, the better. You are determined to use the available means to reduce destruction, but only as long as you still support the government's party objectives.

Given the current government focus on economic growth, you see the sense behind the dam project and are ready to take steps to ensure it is implemented. You want the project to succeed, and you aim to ensure that as much as possible of the financial resources allocated for the construction flows back into the environment, as long as it is successfully implemented. Your commitment lies in finding a balance between environmental protection and economic development.

Your opportunities

You have the authority to issue permits for the dam project, set conditions, expect compensatory measures, and, if necessary, withhold licences. With these powers, the law is on your side, and your decision is crucial. However, you must issue these permits based on

current research. Since permits must undergo a thorough review process within the institute, you cannot make definitive commitments today. Nevertheless, you are confident that ways will be found to issue permits in line with the negotiations, as long as they align with the general goals of the Ministry of the Environment and the government. Your aim is to make a balanced decision that both protects the environment and supports economic development.

Your relationships

As the Minister of the Environment, you maintain close relationships with other members of the government and virtually always support their decisions. You strive to promote their policies through your permits and are therefore in close contact with the President's First Secretary. This often leads to criticism from non-governmental organisations (NGOs), although you personally support their work and are happy to engage with them. You also have a good relationship with the lobby of Volt and Agrimax Innovations and are aware that sooner or later they too will depend on your permits. You like to use the press to bring environmental protection issues to the agenda, always keeping in mind the goal of representing the work of the Ministry of the Environment as particularly sustainable. Recognising your current leverage, you see this as a rare opportunity to push for additional environmental benefits as part of the dam project approvals.

City Mayor

Who you are

As the Mayor of Terra Dourada, you represent the views and needs of the local residents. You are highly respected within the community, particularly among local farmers, and you are committed to advocating for their interests. You are well-acquainted with the concerns and challenges of the people, as you are always present, listening, and taking their issues seriously. Through your direct connection with the farmers, you are aware of the precarious conditions in which they live and are determined to amplify their concerns in these negotiations. You are a member of the Social Democratic Party of Baloria and have strong ties with the local population.

The dam project is one of many issues where you play a crucial role as mayor. You understand the importance of balanced development for your community and seek solutions that consider economic progress, environmental protection, and the quality of life for residents. Born and raised in the community, you know it as a peaceful place and value its tranquillity, stability, and unspoiled nature. Therefore, you prioritise environmental conservation and emphasise a more equitable redistribution of resources and increased funding for the education system over new employment opportunities through the dam project.

For a more authoritative appearance while maintaining a connection to your community, you may choose to wear a smart suit or blazer in neutral tones, paired with a dress shirt or blouse and well-polished shoes. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

Your primary goal is to maintain the support of the local population, as elections are approaching, and you are keen to be re-elected. However, public opinion is divided. While a smaller segment looks forward to new job opportunities, a larger portion strongly opposes the dam project. Their reasons include the destruction of nature, the loss of peace and order in the community due to high migration because of employment opportunities, the impact on the Comnara people who would likely migrate to your community as well, and the destruction of local farmers' livelihoods. The dam brings numerous disadvantages, and you argue firmly against its construction. You also expect local opposition to the dam to grow if the negative impacts on the Comnara and local farmers become visible, given the strong solidarity and long-standing connections among local communities.

The potential migration of the Comnara is particularly concerning. If forced to migrate due to the dam, up to 10,000 Comnara might seek to settle in your community. Changes in water levels in their areas would deprive them of their essential resources. Experience with such large and rapid population movements has shown that affected cities' infrastructure can become overwhelmed, leading to increases in drug use, violence, and prostitution. You see no feasible way for migration to your community to succeed and urgently seek ways to protect the Comnara's territory.

For traditional farming families, you foresee similarly dire consequences from the project. Their situation troubles you. In recent decades, farmers have had to take out increasingly large loans on poor terms due to the modernisation and intensification of agriculture and, most

recently, the privatisation of seeds. Highly indebted, they live in precarious conditions and have limited qualifications to seek other employment. While some may lose their land to the reservoirs, others might be repressed by the large corporation Agrimax Innovations, which plans to establish itself in the region due to the reservoir's water supply. You staunchly defend the rights of the local farmers and strive to stop the project.

If all else fails, you would require substantial financial support and assistance to manage the challenges posed by high labour migration and the displacement of the Comnara. High compensation and relocation payments for the farmers and Comnara are essential. At the same time, you are aware that your community would significantly benefit from the business tax revenue from the hydroelectric plant—funds that could be very useful. Initial economic impact estimates of the dam have somewhat softened your stance, and the potential economic boom for your community has almost made you waver in your opinion. However, you know that the obsession with perpetual economic expansion often ignores the fundamental need to ensure first that basic needs are met for all, rather than indulging in excessive consumption for the wealthy. You criticise mass consumption as you believe it ultimately brings no lasting joy and instead depletes the planet's resources to an irreversible level. This project destroys the harmonious life with each other and with nature – all because the people constantly crave more. Thus, sustainable development and equitable resource distribution should be the primary goals.

Your opportunities

Due to limited financial resources and a relatively weak position of power, your options are constrained. Nevertheless, you have a strong network with the government, NGOs, the local population, and the Comnara. You also use the press to articulate your position, enjoying a dedicated readership that trusts your words. You emphasise legal provisions that support your stance, such as the protection of human rights, the rights of Indigenous peoples, environmental protection, and labour rights according to the Balorian constitution, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, ILO Convention 169, the UN Global Compact (which EnergyGrid Solutions has signed), and the UNDRIP.

Your relationships

As mayor, you maintain regular contact with government representatives, though you often disagree due to differing political positions. You rely on the support of the Comnara and NGOs, maintaining a strong network with them and collaborating whenever possible, and you speak purposefully to the press. Cooperation with the local population, particularly the fishers and farmers, is especially important to you, as you rely on their votes in the upcoming elections.

Volt

Who you are

As the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of Volt, you are an experienced leader and the driving force behind the electric vehicle brand Volt. With a background in electrical engineering and a sharp business acumen, you have transformed Volt into a leading company in the electric vehicle industry. As CEO, you represent the company's vision and goals, making strategic decisions to guide Volt towards sustainable growth and success. You are passionate about developing and implementing promising business strategies to establish Volt worldwide, with headquarters in a rich industrial country in the Global North. Your team has selected Maravilha do Norte, approximately 450 km from the planned dam, as the site for a Gigafactory. This decision followed an intense selection process in which Volt ran a competition for the site. Over a hundred districts, including some from neighbouring countries, applied. Maravilha do Norte was chosen for its strategic location, infrastructure, and potential for sustainable production.

As the CEO of Volt, a sharp and professional appearance can reinforce confidence and leadership during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly. This is purely optional, but you can consider wearing tailored suits or blazers in neutral tones, paired with crisp shirts or blouses. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

The site in Maravilha do Norte, with its affordable labour, political stability, and excellent maritime connections, is your top choice. You have selected this site carefully because it offers optimal conditions for building the Gigafactory. Moreover, you have acted strategically: the political stability in neighbouring countries is not as high, and none of these countries has sufficient renewable energy to power a Gigafactory with green electricity. Therefore, the success of the dam project is particularly important to you. Your goal is to secure at least 200 megawatts reliably from the dam, as maintaining the image of sustainable production is crucial for Volt as a green car brand. Hydropower is ideal for this purpose.

So far, your electric cars have been seen as symbols of exclusivity and high-end technology, accessible only to a limited number of privileged individuals mainly in the global north. You now aim to reduce the costs of your cars by building a Gigafactory in Baloria. With the help of cheap local labour, the unit costs of the cars should be halved within the next 15 years, allowing Volt to produce 2 million cars annually.

To achieve these ambitious goals, several steps must be taken. Necessary infrastructure must be created. Initial designs for this have already been reviewed for approval and are very promising, provided that the entire construction is completed within three years. Therefore, you will only start building the Gigafactory once the dam is nearing completion.

In addition to energy supply, you also need ample water, a reliable rail system, and well-developed roads. There is still much to be done, so it is important to maintain a good relationship with the government and carefully plan and implement all necessary steps.

Your opportunities

Due to the economic impact of your production, you have significant bargaining power, making you a highly sought-after partner for the government. Your supply chain would also be a major economic factor, and although the decision on key suppliers is still pending, you have already informed existing suppliers that they should relocate to Baloria within the next five years to benefit from short delivery routes to Volt and the site's advantages. This makes your company crucial for economic growth in Baloria, and your opinion carries considerable weight in negotiations with the government.

Your position is further strengthened by a recently concluded deal with the President and the President's First Secretary, that was not disclosed publicly, granting you two years of tax-free exports. Although this deal carries some risk, as the President and the government risks their reputation, you consider it a carefully weighed step and ensure it does not become public knowledge.

You also enjoy high regard among many people, especially car enthusiasts and technology companies in the industry. Your social media posts are read by millions. If the dam project fails, you face the challenge of either relocating to another site or finding alternative ways to supply energy—ideally from renewable sources. On the other hand, there is the possibility of sharing profits, and you have financial leeway, which you are reluctant to use. It is up to you to carefully weigh what is best for Volt.

Your relationships

As CEO of Volt, you maintain a close friendship with the First Secretary to the President, and the work of your lobbyists has already secured a good position for Volt within the government. In press interviews, you always emphasise your commitment to the environment, highlighting efforts to advance sustainable solutions and the use of renewable energy in production. Maintaining Volt's image as a green company is of utmost importance to you, and you strive to avoid any risk of losing this image.

You also work to maintain positive relationships with other parties, sometimes choosing not to comment on certain issues or refusing press interviews. In specific conflict situations, you stay back and try to keep out of them to protect Volt's reputation and standing.

Farmers' Association of Baloria

Who you are

As the Chair of the Farmers' Association of Baloria, you grew up in this region and traditionally cultivate manioc, sorghum, and beans for selling, as well as various crops for personal use. You know the region and your 18 hectares of land inside and out, having adapted your farming to changing dry conditions and drought periods. The Duorado River is part of your home, you come from generations of farmers, all of whom worked on a farm. Such a drastic intervention in your life and nature would be hard to watch. Moreover, your land would be almost completely flooded by the largest of the three planned reservoirs. The past few years have been very tough for you. The modernisation and intensification of agriculture have also taken their toll on you. Recently, the privatisation of seeds has forced you to take out loans under bad conditions to cope with the rising prices from seed companies. Around 20,000 other local residents are in similar precarious situations and would also need to relocate or would be repressed by Agrimax Innovations.

As a tidy and organised appearance that still reflects your resilience during the assembly is important to you, you may choose to wear jeans paired with a simple button-down shirt. Remember to engage with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

So far, you and your family have used traditional irrigation farming with diesel and electric pumps. This method has worked well and allowed you to adapt to drier times. Therefore, you are not necessarily dependent on a dam for irrigation. Improved irrigation through the planned reservoir could potentially support about 31 irrigation systems for around 580,000 hectares of agricultural land. This initially appears advantageous. However, your land would be almost completely flooded and you and your family forced to relocate, and you would need to find an alternative way to secure your livelihood. This challenge is further complicated by Agrimax Innovations' plans. The large corporation intends to expand the cultivation of water-intensive crops with the new dam and farm large areas around the reservoir. This would deprive you and your neighbouring farmers in the farmers' association, as you all cannot compete with Agrimax Innovations' production.

Accordingly, you reject the neoliberal ideas of the President and the President's representatives. Due to the lack of access to credit, marketing channels, and information, you feel significantly neglected in the President's "Programme for Accelerated Growth" with your small family farm. Finding another job would be nearly impossible in the current economic situation, especially as you have few other qualifications. With the promotion of less labour-intensive forms of production in agriculture, more and more farmers are becoming unemployed. For you, it is a catastrophe if the remaining farmers also lose their land.

Therefore, you are firmly against the hydroelectric project and argue by citing the negative environmental impacts due to the deforestation of rainforests and the expansion of monocultures by Agrimax Innovations, which severely harm biodiversity. Sometimes you feel that the environment seems to matter more to you than to others – ultimately, mass consumption, especially in the Global North, is incompatible with sustainable resource

management. The mass consumption by the wealthy strikes you as paradoxical – it would be far better to ensure that everyone has enough to live on and that nothing is needlessly wasted.

You also criticise the lack of involvement of affected farmers in the decision-making process so far. However, if solutions for your livelihood were found, you would be willing to compromise with the dam supporters under certain conditions. Simply receiving compensatory land would not be enough with Agrimax Innovations as a competitor. You would expect long-term subsidies for local small farmers and high compensation payments for rebuilding the fields, coupled with relocation costs to move to new areas. Of course, you would also need unrestricted water usage rights from the start.

Your opportunities

Your opportunities are very limited, and you are not well-versed in your rights, relying mainly on empathy and recognition of your situation. You are not keen about the prospect of abandoning the place that has been home for your family over many generations. You have the sympathy of the rural population across the country and use the media extensively to inform others about your situation. At the same time, your financial situation is disastrous: the privatisation of seeds has plunged you and your neighbouring farmers into deep debt cycles, and as a traditional farm worker, you have few job prospects.

Your relationships

As Chair of the Farmers' Association, you work closely with the local mayor and NGOs. You have long had a good relationship with the mayor, trust him, and plan to support his re-election if he continues to uphold your rights and positions in the negotiations. You also have strong sympathies for the positions of the Fisher, who particularly emphasises the local traditional values of the region, and you enjoy working with the Fisher to mobilize the local people. Beyond this, you do not have a strong network, but you use every opportunity to make your voice heard through the press and social media.

Local Fisher

Who You Are

You are a lifelong resident of Terra Dourada, a picturesque region that has been your home for generations. As a fisher, you rely on the rich waters of the local rivers and lakes to provide for your family. Though you and your family live in poverty, with only the bare necessities, you find contentment in the life you've built. Despite the hardships, you take pride in your work and the honest living it provides.

Your neighbourhood is more than just a place you reside; it is a close-knit community where you know everyone by name, and where your neighbours are like extended family. You love the people around you, and you often spend time with them, whether it's sharing stories, helping each other, or gathering for local events. The bond you share with this region runs deep, not only because of its natural beauty but also because it is where your seven sons go to school, and where every path, tree, and stream is familiar to you. Your life is intertwined with the rhythms of the land and water, and you are fiercely protective of the place you call home.

Maintaining a tidy and organized appearance that also reflects your resilience during the assembly is essential to you. Therefore, you may choose to wear jeans paired with a simple button-down shirt, striking a balance between practicality and professionalism. Remember to engage with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your Goals

You are vehemently opposed to the construction of the hydroelectric dam in Terra Dourada. For you, the project represents not just a threat to your livelihood, but an assault on the very fabric of your community. The dam would submerge the fertile fishing grounds that have sustained your family for generations and would destroy the delicate ecosystem that supports both the fish and the people who depend on them.

You argue that the dam is an imposition by distant politicians and corporations who do not understand or value the local way of life. Your primary goal is to preserve Terra Dourada as it is—a thriving, self-sufficient community where people are convinced that the land and water of Terra Dourada are worth more than any promises of economic growth or modernisation. For you, the region's true wealth lies in its traditions, its beautiful relationships, and its close-knit community.

You also wish to ensure that your sons can grow up in the same environment that shaped you—one where they can learn the value of hard work, respect for relationships with nature, and the importance of community ties. You fear that the dam, with its promises of progress, will instead bring disruption, dislocation, and a loss of identity that cannot be measured in monetary terms.

Your Opportunities

While you may not have the financial resources or political influence that others in the negotiations possess, you have the unwavering support of the local community. Your voice represents the concerns of the everyday people who will be most directly affected by the dam.

You have the opportunity to galvanise local opposition, rallying your fellow fishers, farmers, and residents to resist the project. Your deep connection to Terra Dourada gives you a unique perspective that outsiders lack, and you can leverage this to emphasise the long-term consequences of the dam—consequences that those in favour of the project might overlook.

Furthermore, as a respected member of the local community, you can influence public opinion and media coverage by highlighting the human cost of the dam. You can frame the debate not just as an economic issue, but as a matter of preserving a way of life that has intrinsic value beyond what can be measured in profit and loss.

Your Relationships

You maintain a strong relationship with the local mayor of Terra Dourada, who, like you, has deep roots in the community and is sympathetic to your cause. The mayor understands the cultural and environmental significance of the region and has been a vocal advocate for protecting local interests against external pressures.

You are also aligned with the Farmers' Association of Baloria, who share your concerns about the dam's impact on the land. The farmers, who rely on the fertile soil of Terra Dourada for their crops, are natural allies in your fight. They recognise that the dam could lead to the loss of valuable agricultural land, and they stand with you in opposing a project that threatens their livelihoods and the future of their farms.

These relationships are your strongest assets in the negotiation process. By working with the mayor and the farmers, you aim to build a coalition of local stakeholders who can resist the dam's construction and protect Terra Dourada from what you see as an existential threat.

Agrimax Innovations

Who you are

As the CEO of Agrimax Innovations, you head the leading agricultural company on this continent, specialising in the large-scale cultivation of farmland and the production of cost-effective agricultural products. Since its establishment in 2014, Agrimax Innovations has become a dominant player in Baloria's agricultural sector. With its headquarters in a rich industrial country in the Global North, the company operates numerous branches and production facilities on this continent. The land surrounding the proposed dam is not yet in your possession but estimates suggest that the dam could enable around 31 irrigation systems for approximately 580,000 hectares of agricultural land. This makes the area highly attractive to you, and you aim to acquire the farmland around the dam. Agrimax Innovations specialises in growing a variety of crops, including soybeans, maize, sugarcane, and cotton, which are produced mostly for export but also for domestic consumption. By employing cutting-edge agricultural technologies and innovative farming methods, the company maximises yields and runs several research facilities to improve seeds, develop pesticide-resistant plants, and optimise farming techniques.

As the CEO of Agrimax Innovations, a sharp and professional appearance can reinforce confidence and leadership during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly. This is purely optional, but you can consider wearing tailored suits or blazers in neutral tones, paired with crisp shirts or blouses. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

The dam project and the acquisition of the surrounding land are crucial for Agrimax Innovations' strategic goals of increasing yields, ensuring sustainability, and achieving economic stability through long-term investments. The success of the dam project is central to the company, and your strategic objectives include:

1. **Stable water supply:** The dam could provide a consistent water supply, crucial during drought periods, securing crop yields and simplifying production planning.
2. **Increased production capacity:** Improved infrastructure and water availability could allow for larger crop volumes, boosting Agrimax Innovations' market power and revenue. Acquiring new land would further enhance the company's market dominance and monopolistic position in Baloria.
3. **Access to new markets through enhanced irrigation:** The dam could facilitate new irrigation systems, allowing for more intensive and efficient land use, particularly for water-intensive crops, thereby expanding Agrimax Innovations' production portfolio.
4. **Stable energy sources:** The dam would offer a reliable and cost-effective energy source, benefiting Agrimax Innovations' agricultural processing facilities.
5. **Sustainable energy:** Supporting a hydroelectric project aligns with the company's sustainability goals and promotes its image as an environmentally conscious enterprise.

Your risk management and compliance team also endorses the project. Climate change poses increasing risks to water supply stability, and unrestricted water rights from the dam could be crucial in extreme weather situations. Establishing robust flood protection is as important to

you as securing unrestricted water rights, which you will need to negotiate with EnergyGrid Solutions. For successful operations, expanding infrastructure, particularly rail connections, is essential. Since the river will no longer serve as a transport route post-dam, this expansion is vital not just for you but also requires a general rail network enhancement programme, especially towards Baloria's port.

Despite its successes, Agrimax Innovations faces criticism. Environmental groups and local communities accuse the company of contributing to deforestation, biodiversity loss, and jeopardising small farmers' livelihoods through large-scale farming practices. Concerns about the social and ecological impacts of the company's projects, particularly regarding the dam and associated displacement of people, are prevalent. Therefore, you emphasise the dam's renewable energy benefits and promote precision agriculture and numerous social projects aimed at improving rural life to portray Agrimax Innovations as a sustainable and socially responsible company.

Your opportunities

As a large corporation, you have various means to assert your will in negotiations. The company has sufficient capital not only to purchase adjacent farmland but also to support compensatory offers for affected communities and the environment if necessary. Implementing environmental and social programmes can effectively reduce resistance and garner support. Through targeted public relations and media campaigns, Agrimax Innovations can highlight the dam's benefits and influence public opinion, supported by credible studies, expert opinions, and reports. Besides your financial leverage, you have strong partnerships and connections within the government. Agrimax Innovations has engaged in extensive lobbying to secure political backing for the dam project and integrate its interests into the growth programme, including promoting legislative changes.

Your relationships

Agrimax Innovations maintains close ties with key political and media figures to successfully implement its projects and goals. The company collaborates with renowned environmental and technical experts to produce scientific studies and reports supporting its initiatives, which, while not present today, you can refer to. In media relations, Agrimax Innovations employs strategic public relations, including press conferences, informational events, and extensive media campaigns, to communicate the benefits of its initiatives and foster a positive public perception.

EnergyGrid Solutions

Who you are

As the CEO of EnergyGrid Solutions, the largest energy company in Baloria and the operator of the proposed dam project, the responsibility for the subsequent operation of the hydroelectric plant lies in your hands. You have an impressive career in the energy sector and possess a deep understanding of the complexities of the energy market. Shares of EnergyGrid Solutions are already traded on the stock exchanges in São Paulo, Madrid, and New York, with the company being predominantly state-owned. Despite the prestigious position and financial success of EnergyGrid Solutions, you feel a certain frustration. Your predecessor signed the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) on behalf of the company, publicly committing to the responsible management of natural resources and the protection of biodiversity. While you personally share these values, you find the obligation to continue representing them an additional burden. You would prefer to focus on business expansion and driving innovation rather than spending time and resources on sustainability initiatives.

For a more authoritative appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a professional suit or blazer, enhanced by accessories such as ties or subtle pins. While optional, this attire can project confidence and reinforce your presence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

For EnergyGrid Solutions, the proposed dam project is the flagship project of the century, and you are fully committed to ensuring it becomes a reality. You have already invested significant resources in this project, and failure would not only be a massive setback for the company but could also have serious consequences on the solvency of EnergyGrid Solutions and EnergyGrid Alliance.

With a view to current market changes, you aim to increase the share of renewable energy in the energy mix. The EnergyGrid Alliance team has already commissioned an environmental impact assessment to lay the groundwork for obtaining the necessary permits for the large-scale project from the Ministry of the Environment. While the assessment identified the loss of unknown species, you are convinced that the economic benefits of the dam outweigh the potential drawbacks. You also argue that hydropower is a necessary alternative to at least partially move away from coal power. The primary goal, therefore, is for the dam project to succeed. Much work has already gone into it, and its realisation promises not only many new jobs but also an impressive symbol and attraction for the region and EnergyGrid Solutions.

The situation with the Comnara and the local farmers is concerning to you. While you recognise their precarious conditions, you cannot provide high compensation payments. Therefore, you try to transfer the burden of environmental compensation, compensation payments, and resettlement costs to the local community, the government, or companies like Agrimax Innovations (regarding the farmers) and Volt. You believe that any complications arising during construction, such as filling the reservoirs, are the responsibility of EnergyGrid Alliance. However, as a major shareholder of EnergyGrid Alliance, you cannot easily offload these debts onto them.

As a way to shift the debate in your favour, you can highlight the job creation and economic growth expected from the dam and, by extension, from Volt and Agrimax Innovations.

Your opportunities

As the CEO of EnergyGrid Solutions, you feel a certain gratitude towards the President and the President's representatives, who played a key role in making EnergyGrid Solutions the operator of the dam project. This gratitude brings with it a sense of obligation, prompting you to remain loyal to the President's policies, even if it occasionally leads to conflicts with other stakeholders.

In your role, you often find yourself driven to and from like a plaything between government interests and the demands of other parties. The idea of finding an alternative site for the proposed dam project seems nearly impossible to you, as the current location is geographically almost perfect. Although you are aware that wind power could be a possible alternative, the already invested amount in the dam project is substantial. EnergyGrid Solutions' resources are limited, and a complete shift to wind power would be a financial disaster. Hence, you do not even consider proposing this option. Financially, you are already hoping that the government will grant you low lease rates for the land of the hydroelectric plant and reservoirs.

During negotiations, you also expect Agrimax Innovations and individual farmers to demand unrestricted access to the reservoir water. You have already accounted for agricultural water use in the planning of the hydroelectric plant, so you could provide them with the necessary water. At the same time, you see yourself as the leaseholder of the water in the reservoirs, possessing the rights to it, and hope to exert pressure on the agricultural industry, particularly Agrimax Innovations, if necessary. However, keep in mind that this could strain relations with an important supporter of the dam project, which you cannot afford to lose for the joint strategic negotiations.

After the engineers from EnergyGrid Alliance's construction planning team determined that reducing the number of reservoirs would also result in a reduction to 5,000 megawatts, you opposed this option. You are firmly convinced that this is insufficient, especially considering that Volt alone has a demand of 200 megawatts. As the largest energy supplier in the country, your team has a comprehensive understanding of the energy needs. Nonetheless, any dam is better than none.

Your relationships

As the CEO of EnergyGrid Solutions, you not only have a good understanding of the business strategies of the CEOs of Volt and Agrimax Innovations but also maintain good relationships with them. Your relationship with the First Secretary to the President and the ministers of the government is particularly close.

For years, you have maintained close collaboration, and since the state is the main shareholder of EnergyGrid Solutions, you are dependent on them. You also work closely with EnergyGrid Alliance, sharing the same goals. In relation to the press, you strive for a reliable and professional image and support the government's efforts to present Baloria as an attractive business location. Since the industry is an important client for EnergyGrid Solutions, this is also a concern for you. To avoid conflicts and not strain relations with the government, you avoid controversial questions or conflicts in the media and refuse to answer, if necessary, to protect the public image of EnergyGrid Solutions and Baloria.

EnergyGrid Alliance

Who you are

For the dam project, various stakeholders have formed a construction consortium named EnergyGrid Alliance. As the contract manager within this consortium, you are responsible for managing all contracts related to the construction project. Your main task is to ensure that all contracts are properly negotiated, concluded, and adhered to, ensuring the smooth implementation of the project. Thanks to your diplomatic skills, you represent the EnergyGrid Alliance in negotiations and fully support the project.

EnergyGrid Alliance won the government contract to auction the construction and operating rights. The consortium is thus responsible for the planning and design of the dam, financing, construction management, responsibility for environmental and social compatibility, as well as stakeholder management. After successful construction, operations will be handled by the majority state-owned power provider EnergyGrid Solutions. EnergyGrid Solutions already owns 47.9% of the consortium. The second-largest shareholder is the Global Development Bank (GDB) with 12.3%. The project is also supported by significant funds from Balorian pension funds and private investors, including national mining companies with an interest in nearby mines and various international funds, banks, and asset managers. Following the recent exit of three shareholders due to the latest lawsuit, you now worry that further resistance could also deter other investors. Therefore, you fight with all means for the success of the project and strive to project confidence.

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Your goals

As a contract manager, it is important to you to combine the expertise, resources, and capacities of several companies and the government to implement the project efficiently and effectively. The goal is to build a dam that provides long-term benefits to the region and society as a whole while ensuring economic profitability. You argue that the dam project will create jobs and contribute to economic development in the region. You also emphasise hydropower as a clean energy source that helps reduce dependency on fossil fuels.

In response to the project's opponents, you refer to the results of an environmental impact assessment and individual public hearings conducted by your team to obtain the necessary permits. The same procedure will be followed with the remaining pending permits. The environmental impact assessment, conducted by an independent institute on your behalf, was a strategic step to publicly highlight EnergyGrid Alliance's sustainability efforts. While it identified the loss of certain unexplored species, you are convinced that the economic benefits far outweigh these disadvantages.

Your opportunities

For you, abandoning the project is not an option. The possibility of reducing the number of reservoirs to one has already been discussed among your engineers. This would lower the generated energy to 5,000 megawatts. EnergyGrid Solutions has clearly opposed this, as the generated energy would be insufficient for Baloria, especially considering that Volt alone has a demand of 200 megawatts. You fully trust EnergyGrid Solutions in this assessment, as they are the largest energy provider in the country with a comprehensive understanding of the energy needs. Additionally, reducing the number of reservoirs would not change the situation for the Comnara, but for some local farmers at least.

If you cannot implement the project as planned, you seek compromises through compensation areas and payments. Although you are reluctant to incur more debt and worry about investor approval, anything is better than the project's failure. Perhaps there is a possibility of relocating the Comnara and the local farmers or providing compensation areas in the tropical rainforest, which you financially place under special protection, or other compensation measures such as promoting specific social projects. Payments to NGOs might even be a way to quieten them down as well.

Your relationships

As a contract manager, you collaborate closely with the government and all other supporters of the dam project. You not only have a solid understanding of the business strategies pursued by the CEOs of Volt and Agrimax Innovations, but you also maintain strong working relationships with them. Additionally, you work in close partnership with EnergyGrid Solutions, sharing common objectives—making it strategically beneficial to build a firm alliance with them.

In contrast, you are reluctant to engage with NGOs. You do not acknowledge the Comnara as a legitimate stakeholder and question their claim to the land, seeing no reason why it should belong more to them than to you. Consequently, you avoid direct contact with them.

Similarly, you question why the 20,000 local residents should be given greater respect and consideration than the nation's energy security. When it comes to dealing with the press, you are often reserved—declining to comment when necessary and routinely emphasising the importance of prior agreements with investors before making public statements.

Global Development Bank

Who You Are

You are the Chairperson of the Global Development Bank (GDB), a key institution that plays a significant role in financing large-scale infrastructure projects across the globe. The GDB is one of the most significant shareholders of EnergyGrid Alliance, holding 12.3% of the consortium's shares. This makes your bank a crucial player in the decision-making process and directly involves you in the dam project in Terra Dourada. Your role requires a keen understanding of both the financial and socio-political implications of such projects, and you are deeply invested in ensuring the success of the dam project.

The GDB is not merely a financial backer but also a guardian of environmental and social standards. You oversee the monitoring of social-ecological measures as stipulated in the environmental licences, which are crucial for the project's progression. With construction and financial support already approved, your primary concern is ensuring that all legal and environmental requirements are met to release the necessary funds. Your interest in the project's success is not just professional but also tied to the bank's reputation and the broader strategic goals of promoting sustainable development through infrastructure investment.

For a more authoritative appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a professional suit or blazer, enhanced by accessories such as ties or minimalist jewellery. While optional, this attire can project your success and reinforce your presence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both those you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your Goals

Your main goal is to see the dam project in Terra Dourada successfully completed, as it aligns with the GDB's mission to support projects that foster economic growth and development. You view the dam as a vital piece of infrastructure that will not only provide clean energy to Baloria but also stimulate the local economy, create jobs, and attract further investments. As a significant shareholder, you are fully aligned with the objectives of EnergyGrid Alliance, and you support their efforts to navigate the complexities of this large-scale project.

A crucial aspect of your goals is ensuring that the dam project adheres to all environmental regulations and maintains its social licence to operate. You are aware that the project's success hinges on presenting valid and up-to-date environmental licences, which are under the scrutiny of your bank. The social-ecological measures outlined in the licensing requirements must be rigorously followed, as any failure to do so could jeopardise the project and lead to financial losses for the GDB. Therefore, you are committed to supporting the project while ensuring that it meets the high standards expected by the international community.

Your Opportunities

As the Chairperson of the GDB, you hold significant influence over the project's financing and its compliance with environmental and social standards. This gives you the opportunity to shape the project in a way that maximises both its economic benefits and its alignment with sustainable development goals. You can leverage your position to ensure that the project

remains on track by advocating for strict adherence to the social-ecological measures and by pushing for transparency and accountability within EnergyGrid Alliance.

Moreover, your role allows you to engage with other key stakeholders, including the government of Baloria, to secure the necessary support and approvals for the project. You also have the opportunity to present the GDB as a leader in sustainable development financing by ensuring that the dam project meets the highest environmental and social standards. This would not only enhance the bank's reputation but also set a precedent for future projects, potentially attracting more investors to the GDB's portfolio.

In the event of challenges, such as legal disputes or resistance from local communities, you have the flexibility to negotiate compromises, such as the provision of compensation areas or support for social projects that could mitigate opposition. These opportunities allow you to balance the bank's financial interests with its commitment to sustainable development.

Your Relationships

Your role involves close collaboration with various stakeholders, both within the EnergyGrid Alliance and externally. As the GDB's representative, you maintain strong relationships with government officials, ensuring that the project aligns with national development goals and receives the necessary political backing. Your connections within the consortium, particularly with EnergyGrid Solutions, are crucial for coordinating efforts and ensuring that the project progresses smoothly.

While you generally avoid direct engagement with NGOs, you recognise the importance of addressing their concerns to avoid potential delays or conflicts. You prefer to deal with these organisations through formal channels, ensuring that any agreements or concessions are carefully negotiated to protect the GDB's interests.

Your relationship with the media is cautious. You understand the power of public perception and therefore approach press interactions with care, often referring to the need for prior agreements with investors before making any public statements. You aim to project confidence in the project's success while maintaining a focus on the GDB's role as a responsible investor committed to sustainable development.

EcoVision Global: Policy Advisor

Who you are

As a policy advisor at the international NGO EcoVision Global, you are an experienced force in an organisation dedicated to environmental protection worldwide. EcoVision Global is primarily funded by donations to maintain independence from business and political influences. Due to the limited financial resources provided by donations, you have had little opportunity to extensively study the political and economic situation of Baloria. This makes it challenging for you to present well-founded arguments regarding the country's economy. You come from a wealthy nation that has already invested significantly in green technologies. You understand the immense importance of protecting the tropical rainforest and believe that Baloria, despite its economic situation, bears full responsibility for environmental protection. As a long-standing policy advisor, you are weary of witnessing corruption and flawed democracy, sometimes feeling that the real aim of such projects is not energy production but rather to support corruption schemes with contractors and political parties.

For a professional appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a blazer paired with a shirt or blouse in neutral tones, prioritizing eco-friendly fabrics or sustainably produced brands. While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

Together with the national environmental protection NGO "Sustainability Network Baloria," you have formulated the following goals:

1. Immediate halt to the planning and construction of the hydroelectric power plant.
2. Full compliance with human rights, Indigenous peoples' rights, environmental protection, and labour rights as per the Balorian constitution, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, ILO Convention 169, the UN Global Compact, and the UNDRIP.
3. Active promotion of renewable energy sources and the provision of public loans for the development of solar and wind energy in particular.
4. Replacement of the planned output of the hydroelectric power plant with a combination of clean renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and/or biomass energy) and steps towards energy reduction.
5. Combating corruption in the Balorian energy and agriculture sectors.
6. Profits should not end up in the hands of the super-rich: Decision-making processes must involve the local population to prevent hierarchies from being exploited and profits from being unjustly transferred to the Global North.

Overall, you consider the dam project an absolute disaster and strategically aim to highlight the negative impacts of the dam. You also support the protection of local farmers, as Agrimax Innovations' monocultures and the increased use of pesticides by the company causes

massive destruction of biodiversity. You emphasise the risk that interference with watercourses can lead to massive destruction of vast areas of alluvial forests, which depend on seasonal flooding. This affects not only the directly flooded area but also involves a profound intervention in a far-reaching ecosystem, hundreds of kilometres upstream and downstream. Previous large-scale projects in the tropical rainforest have shown that the construction of roads and other infrastructure also promotes illegal mining, agriculture, and logging, leading to even more destruction.

Point 6 is particularly important to the NGO Sustainability Network Baloria. You also recognise its significance and are aware of the enormous power hierarchies, especially those involving actors from the Global North. If the hydroelectric plant proceeds, it is foreseeable that substantial profits will flow to the North through Volt and involved construction companies, while dependency and irreversible resource consumption will dominate locally. Similarly, a significant portion of Agrimax Innovations' production is exported despite clear local needs.

Additionally, you want to debunk the understanding of hydropower as 'green energy.' In the short term, dams emit significant amounts of greenhouse gases, mainly carbon dioxide and methane, due to the decomposition of flooded vegetation and soil. Moreover, the energy and resources required to construct such large-scale projects are immense. The contribution of dams to global warming is substantial and comparable to half that of an equivalent gas-powered plant. Furthermore, your team suspects that the new dam project will struggle to generate the planned amount of energy due to climate change and the associated reduction in water flow in the region. Seasonal river fluctuations could further reduce energy production. Additionally, the dam may cause flooding, fish population declines, and ecosystem damage, threatening local jobs and wellbeing dependent on these resources.

To mitigate these negative aspects, you advocate for designating areas, particularly the alluvial forests below the proposed dam, as special protected areas with access only for local and Indigenous communities. You also try to shift the discussion towards alternative energy generation methods, especially wind and solar power, and consider options for energy reduction.

Your opportunities

You enjoy immense global attention from the general public. Your voice is heard in the media and shapes the opinions of many people. You can leverage this reach to emphasise that EnergyGrid Solutions is not adhering to the signed UN Global Compact. Your investigations reveal that both the company and its supporters are violating the agreements mentioned in Goal 2. You also focus on the devastating impacts the project has on the Comnara.

Furthermore, you have strong arguments to criticise the Ministry of the Environment's permits. These permits are all based on the environmental impact assessment (EIA) commissioned by EnergyGrid Alliance. This EIA identified 2,400 new species around the proposed dam, some of which are endangered. However, EcoVision Global's investigations found that habitats downstream of the proposed dam were not considered in any samples or modelling. Additionally, the risks to many species associated with altered river water levels were inadequately analysed. Such an incomplete study should never serve as the basis for approvals, and your goal is to ensure that both the public and the Ministry of the Environment recognise this flaw. This also challenges the Volt CEO's claim that his company is sustainable, given these serious environmental oversights.

Your relationships

You work side by side with the Sustainability Network Baloria, the Comnara, the mayor and the local farmers, thus supporting all arguments against the large-scale project. This brings you into high conflict potential with representatives of the government, EnergyGrid Solutions, and EnergyGrid Alliance. The press, however, pays strong attention to you. Use this to your advantage!

EcoVision Global: Public Relations Officer

Who You Are

As the Public Relations Officer of EcoVision Global, you are the voice and public face of an influential international NGO dedicated to environmental protection. EcoVision Global, largely funded by donations, prides itself on maintaining independence from business and political influences. Your role is crucial in shaping the public image of the organisation, ensuring that its mission and objectives are communicated effectively to the broader public, stakeholders, and the media. You work closely with the Policy Advisor, sharing the same goals but with a focus on managing the organisation's external communications. This involves crafting and disseminating compelling narratives through press releases, social media, and public statements that highlight the importance of environmental protection and the dangers posed by the dam project in Terra Dourada.

You are deeply committed to the cause, using your expertise to raise awareness and rally public support against the dam. Coming from a country with advanced green technologies, you understand the critical need for protecting the tropical rainforest and believe that Baloria, despite its economic challenges, has a responsibility to uphold environmental and human rights. You have a keen sense of the power dynamics at play, especially regarding the exploitation of natural resources by entities from the Global North, and you strive to expose and counter these injustices.

For a professional appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a blazer paired with a shirt or blouse in neutral tones, prioritizing eco-friendly fabrics or sustainably produced brands. While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your Goals

Together with the national environmental protection NGO "Sustainability Network Baloria," you have formulated the following goals:

1. Immediate halt to the planning and construction of the hydroelectric power plant.
2. Full compliance with human rights, indigenous peoples' rights, environmental protection, and labour rights as per the Balorian constitution, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, ILO Convention 169, the UN Global Compact, and the UNDRIP.
3. Active promotion of renewable energy sources and the provision of public loans for the development of solar and wind energy in particular.
4. Replacement of the planned output of the hydroelectric power plant with a combination of clean renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and/or biomass energy) and steps towards energy reduction.
5. Combating corruption in the Balorian energy and agriculture sectors.

6. Profits should not end up in the hands of the super-rich: Decision-making processes must involve the local population to prevent hierarchies from being exploited and profits from being unjustly transferred to the Global North.

Overall, you consider the dam project an absolute disaster and strategically aim to highlight the negative impacts of the dam. You also support the protection of local farmers, as Agrimax Innovations' monocultures and the increased use of pesticides by the company causes massive destruction of biodiversity. You emphasise the risk that interference with watercourses can lead to massive destruction of vast areas of alluvial forests, which depend on seasonal flooding. This affects not only the directly flooded area but also involves a profound intervention in a far-reaching ecosystem, hundreds of kilometres upstream and downstream. Previous large-scale projects in the tropical rainforest have shown that the construction of roads and other infrastructure also promotes illegal mining, agriculture, and logging, leading to even more destruction.

Point 6 is particularly important to the NGO Sustainability Network Baloria. You also recognise its significance and are aware of the enormous power hierarchies, especially those involving actors from the Global North. If the hydroelectric plant proceeds, it is foreseeable that substantial profits will flow to the North through Volt and involved construction companies, while dependency and irreversible resource consumption will dominate locally. Similarly, a significant portion of Agrimax Innovations' production is exported despite clear local needs.

Additionally, you want to debunk the understanding of hydropower as "green energy." In the short term, dams emit significant amounts of greenhouse gases, mainly carbon dioxide and methane, due to the decomposition of flooded vegetation and soil. Moreover, the energy and resources required to construct such large-scale projects are immense. The contribution of dams to global warming is substantial and comparable to half that of an equivalent gas-powered plant. Furthermore, your team suspects that the new dam project will struggle to generate the planned amount of energy due to climate change and the associated reduction in water flow in the region. Seasonal river fluctuations could further drastically reduce energy production. Additionally, the dam may cause flooding, fish population declines, and ecosystem damage, threatening local jobs and wellbeing dependent on these resources.

To mitigate these negative aspects, you advocate for designating areas, particularly the alluvial forests below the proposed dam, as special protected areas with access only for local and indigenous communities. You also try to shift the discussion towards alternative energy generation methods, especially wind and solar power, and consider options for energy reduction.

Your Opportunities

As the Public Relations Officer, you have a powerful platform to influence public opinion and shape the narrative around the dam project. Your role gives you access to the media, where your statements and press releases can garner significant attention. This media exposure is a critical tool in your strategy to raise awareness about the environmental and social consequences of the dam, putting pressure on both the government of Baloria and the consortium behind the project.

You also have the opportunity to mobilise global support through campaigns that highlight the failures of the EnergyGrid Alliance to adhere to international environmental standards, such as those outlined in the UN Global Compact. By exposing shortcomings of the environmental impact assessment (EIA) conducted by the consortium, you can challenge the legitimacy of the project's environmental licences and push for a more thorough and independent review. The permits for the dam are all based on the environmental impact assessment (EIA) commissioned by EnergyGrid Alliance. This EIA identified 2400 new species around the proposed dam, some of which are endangered. However, EcoVision Global's investigations found that habitats downstream of the proposed dam were not considered in any samples or modelling. Additionally, the risks to many species associated with altered river water levels were inadequately analysed. Such an incomplete study should never serve as the basis for approvals, and your goal is to ensure that both the public and the Ministry of Environment recognise this flaw. This also challenges the Volt CEO's claim that his company is sustainable, given these serious environmental oversights.

Your ability to engage with the global community, including donors, activists, and sympathetic governments, allows you to build a coalition of support against the dam. This international pressure can be a decisive factor in swaying the Balorian government and investors to reconsider the project.

Your Relationships

Your work brings you into close collaboration with several key groups opposed to the dam. You maintain strong ties with the national environmental NGO Sustainability Network Baloria, and you actively support the local farmers and the Indigenous Comnara community. These relationships are vital for coordinating efforts to stop the project and for amplifying the voices of those most directly affected by the dam.

However, your position also puts you in direct conflict with powerful stakeholders, including representatives of the Balorian government, EnergyGrid Solutions, and the EnergyGrid Alliance. Navigating these relationships requires careful diplomacy and strategic communication, particularly when dealing with the press. Your ability to maintain a consistent and compelling message is crucial in keeping public attention focused on the environmental and social justice issues at the heart of the debate.

You also recognise the importance of international solidarity and regularly engage with global media outlets to ensure that EcoVision Global's perspective reaches a wide audience. By effectively leveraging your media relationships, you can keep the dam project under intense scrutiny and build the public pressure needed to achieve your organisation's goals.

Sustainability Network Baloria: Project Manager

Who you are

In your position as project manager at the Sustainability Network Baloria, you hold significant responsibility that extends beyond simply managing projects such as the fight against the dam project. As a central figure in the organisation, you are responsible for the smooth execution of projects and the adherence to ethical principles within the NGO, participating in key negotiations like this one.

In your role, you work closely with national and international experts to ensure that the NGO's projects meet the highest quality standards and achieve the intended positive impact. Together with the NGO EcoVision Global and other actors, you played a key role in filing the lawsuit against the dam project to enforce environmental and Indigenous rights protections.

Financially, the Sustainability Network Baloria faces challenges due to its primarily donation-based funding and heavy reliance on volunteer work. Previously, when offered funds by a member of the ruling party, you visibly wavered and only weakly decided against it. However, your ability to tackle complex challenges between politics, economics, and the environment makes you a key figure in the pursuit of sustainable development and social justice.

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Your goals

Together with the international environmental protection NGO "EcoVision Global" you have formulated the following five goals:

1. Immediate halt to the planning and construction of the hydroelectric power plant.
2. Full compliance with human rights, indigenous peoples' rights, environmental protection, and labour rights as per the Balorian constitution, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, ILO Convention 169, the UN Global Compact, and the UNDRIP.
3. Active promotion of renewable energy sources and the provision of public loans for the development of solar and wind energy in particular.
4. Replacement of the planned output of the hydroelectric power plant with a combination of clean renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and/or biomass energy) and steps towards energy reduction.
5. Combating corruption in the Balorian energy and agriculture sectors.
6. Profits should not end up in the hands of the super-rich: Decision-making processes must involve the local population to prevent hierarchies from being exploited and profits from being unjustly transferred to the Global North.

In this project against the dam, you are committed to preserving the territories where the Comnara have resided over generations. Under all circumstances, you strive to ensure that these territories are not threatened by any disturbances. This means that the undisturbed flow of the river must be guaranteed. Therefore, you find it unacceptable for this site to be considered for a hydroelectric power plant and actively advocate for alternative energy sources to be considered. You believe that Baloria could take a significant step by protecting this area and designating it as a nature reserve. You think that nature is worth protecting for its own sake, regardless of its benefits for air and climate, and occasionally highlight the impressive characteristics of the tropical rainforest and the fascination it inspires.

Furthermore, you support the protection of local farmers, as Agrimax Innovations' monocultures and increased use of pesticides by the corporation cause massive destruction of biodiversity. You are in good contact with them and try to change the precarious circumstances in which they live. Economically, you are very aware of Baloria's financial situation and recognise the need to create new jobs. However, you mainly appeal for a fairer redistribution of resources, including a higher inheritance tax on the super-rich and greater investments in the education and healthcare sectors. You are firmly convinced that the large project will ultimately disappoint the people of Baloria, as it will only bring wealth to a few companies while enormous sums of Balorian tax money will be lost through the promises made by the President.

In addition to this, you feel a strong anger fueled by the stark dimensions of power abuse and economic exploitation by countries from the Global North. Again and again, you witness how these powerful entities manipulate large-scale projects to strip Baloria's resources at minimal cost, leaving locals dependent and impoverished. Their influence permeates our governments, corrupting decision-making processes and ensuring that profits are siphoned off to the North while our communities languish in poverty. The case of this dam is a glaring example: even before Volt and Agrimax Innovations had more influence over the dam than the Comnara or the farmers, the profits of many foreign construction companies, Volt and Agrimax Innovations will flow to the Global North. Despite the dire need for food in the region, most of Agrimax Innovations' production will be exported to wealthier nations. This systemic exploitation not only stifles development but also perpetuates a cycle of dependency and deprivation. It is high time these injustices were addressed, and the strong hierarchies were exposed to the public. You believe that it has to go hand in hand with the development of an energy system that is both climate-friendly and conducive to development. Therefore, you urge all companies and banks involved in this project to support Baloria in developing a sustainable and just energy system.

Your opportunities

You enjoy immense attention from the public in Baloria. Your voice is heard in the media and shapes the opinions of many people. You can leverage this reach to call the public to protest. Use the media to call for a mass demonstration and mobilise people from all walks of life.

In the dialogue assembly, you can also emphasise that EnergyGrid Solutions is not adhering to the signed UN Global Compact. Your investigations, together with EcoVision Global, show that both the company and its supporters are violating the agreements mentioned in Goal 2. The law is thus partly on your side, and you can argue this point.

Your relationships

Your goal is clear: you aim for a strong alliance of all project opponents. You repeatedly appeal for alliances with all civil society actors and the mayor and do not shy away from conflicts with project supporters. For you, the press is a powerful tool to mobilise the public and raise awareness of the injustices. Use it strategically, as it can help amplify the voices of those opposing the project and increase pressure on decision-makers. Your ability to forge alliances and skilfully use the media makes you a driving force in the fight against the project.

Sustainability Network Baloria: Policy Advisor

Who You Are

As the Policy Advisor for the Sustainability Network Baloria, you play a pivotal role in shaping the organisation's political strategy and advocating for sustainable development. Your expertise lies in understanding the complex interplay between environmental protection, social justice, and economic policy, which you leverage to influence political decisions at the local and national levels. Working closely with the Project Manager and other team members, you help craft the NGO's approach to achieving its mission, particularly in the context of the dam project in Terra Dourada. Your responsibilities extend beyond mere advisory tasks; you are deeply involved in the strategic planning of campaigns, policy proposals, and public statements.

With a background in environmental policy and a strong intrinsic interest in social equity, you are committed to ensuring that the voices of marginalised communities, like the Indigenous Comnara, are heard and respected in all decisions impacting their lands and lives. You are acutely aware of the environmental, social, and economic implications of large-scale infrastructure projects like the dam and are determined to prevent what you see as a potentially catastrophic development for Baloria.

Financially, the Sustainability Network Baloria faces challenges due to its primarily donation-based funding and heavy reliance on volunteer work. Previously, when offered funds by a member of the ruling party, you visibly wavered and only weakly decided against it. However, your ability to tackle complex challenges between politics, economics, and the environment makes you a key figure in the pursuit of sustainable development and social justice.

For a professional appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may opt for a blazer paired with a shirt or blouse in neutral tones, prioritizing eco-friendly fabrics or sustainably produced brands. While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your Goals

Together with the international environmental protection NGO "EcoVision Global" you have formulated the following five goals:

1. Immediate halt to the planning and construction of the hydroelectric power plant.
2. Full compliance with human rights, Indigenous peoples' rights, environmental protection, and labour rights as per the Balorian constitution, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, ILO Convention 169, the UN Global Compact, and the UNDRIP.
3. Active promotion of renewable energy sources and the provision of public loans for the development of solar and wind energy in particular.
4. Replacement of the planned output of the hydroelectric power plant with a combination of clean renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and/or biomass energy) and steps towards energy reduction.

5. Combating corruption in the Balorian energy and agricultural sectors.
6. Profits should not end up in the hands of the super-rich: Decision-making processes must involve the local population to prevent hierarchies from being exploited and profits from being unjustly transferred to the Global North.

In this project against the dam, you are committed to preserving the territories where the Comnara have resided over generations. Under all circumstances, you strive to ensure that these territories are not threatened by any disturbances. This means that the undisturbed flow of the river must be guaranteed. Therefore, you find it unacceptable for this site to be considered for a hydroelectric power plant and actively advocate for alternative energy sources to be considered. You believe that Baloria could take a significant step by protecting this area and designating it as a nature reserve. You think that nature is worth protecting for its own sake, regardless of its benefits for air and climate, and occasionally highlight the impressive characteristics of the tropical rainforest and the fascination it inspires.

Furthermore, you support the protection of local farmers, as Agrimax Innovations' monocultures and increased use of pesticides by the corporation cause massive destruction of biodiversity. You are in good contact with them and try to change the precarious circumstances in which they live. Economically, you are very aware of Baloria's financial situation and recognise the need to create new jobs. However, you mainly appeal for a fairer redistribution of resources, including a higher inheritance tax on the super-rich and greater investments in the education and healthcare sectors. You are firmly convinced that the large project will ultimately disappoint the people of Baloria, as it will only bring wealth to a few companies while enormous sums of Balorian tax money will be lost through the promises made by the President.

In addition to this, you feel a strong anger fuelled by the stark dimensions of power abuse and economic exploitation by countries from the Global North. Again and again, you witness how these powerful entities manipulate large-scale projects to strip Baloria's resources at minimal cost, leaving locals dependent and impoverished. Their influence permeates our governments, corrupting decision-making processes and ensuring that profits are siphoned off to the North while our communities languish in poverty. The case of this dam is a glaring example: even before Volt and Agrimax Innovations had more influence over the dam than the Comnara or the farmers, the profits of many foreign construction companies, Volt and Agrimax Innovations will flow to the Global North. Despite the dire need for food in the region, most of Agrimax Innovations' production will be exported to wealthier nations. This systemic exploitation not only stifles development but also perpetuates a cycle of dependency and deprivation. It is high time these injustices were addressed, and the strong hierarchies were exposed to the public. You believe that it has to go hand in hand with the development of an energy system that is both climate-friendly and conducive to development. Therefore, you urge all companies and banks involved in this project to support Baloria in developing a sustainable and just energy system.

Your Opportunities

As the Policy Advisor, you have significant influence in shaping public discourse around the dam project. Your role allows you to engage directly with policymakers, presenting well-researched arguments that highlight the flaws in the project's planning and the long-term risks it poses. Your expertise in policy and environmental law provides you with the tools to

challenge the legal and ethical foundations of the project, particularly in relation to its compliance with international agreements and environmental standards.

You also have the opportunity to mobilise public opinion against the dam. Through your strategic use of media and public statements, you can raise awareness of the negative impacts of the dam, galvanising support for your cause both within Baloria and internationally. Your ability to articulate a compelling alternative vision for Baloria's energy future can attract broader support, including from other NGOs, international organisations, and sympathetic governments.

In the dialogue assembly, you can also emphasise that EnergyGrid Solutions is not adhering to the signed UN Global Compact. Your investigations, together with EcoVision Global, show that both the company and its supporters are violating the agreements mentioned in Goal 2. The law is thus partly on your side, and you can argue this point.

Your Relationships

In your role, you work closely with a broad coalition of allies who share your opposition to the dam. These include the Sustainability Network Baloria, EcoVision Global, local farmers, the Comnara community, and other civil society organisations. Your relationship with these groups is collaborative, and you play a key role in coordinating their efforts and ensuring that their voices are heard in the negotiation process.

However, you are also in direct conflict with powerful stakeholders who support the dam, including representatives from the Balorian government, EnergyGrid Solutions, and foreign investors. Navigating these relationships requires a careful balance of diplomacy and assertiveness, as you seek to hold these actors accountable while advocating for the rights of local communities.

The media is a crucial ally in your efforts. By skilfully managing your public relations, you can ensure that your message reaches a wide audience, amplifying the voices of those who stand to lose the most from the dam project.

Comnara: Educator

Who you are

You are a member of the Indigenous Comnara community and you are mainly caring for the children of your community. Your community inhabit an area of about 2,319,000 hectares, roughly the size of Wales. The history of the Comnara is particularly renowned for the intense trade in the 19th century, which significantly shaped your culture and way of life. The Comnara community consists of five distinct regional groups, one of which is further divided into subgroups. Altogether, you represent about 10,000 people who share a rich cultural heritage and a strong sense of community. History and traditions are a vital part of the Comnara and therefore also for you, deeply influencing your daily life and your relationships in the community and with the environment. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

To represent the interests of the Comnara, you work closely with the Comnara mediator. While the proposed dam would not directly flood Comnara territory, it would significantly disrupt your way of life. The diversion of the river would devastate your fishing, groundwater resources, and river transport, forcing many Comnara people into involuntary relocation. Additionally, stagnant water could promote waterborne diseases. The environmental impact assessment commissioned by EnergyGrid Alliance, which serves as the basis for the dam's approval, is laughable to you. It fails to consider these critical factors, and you're appalled that such a massive environmental intrusion is reduced to a few aspects of species loss. Your goal is to highlight the environmental impacts from your perspective and to prevent the dam and similar projects from proceeding. Once the dam is operational, the river, which is central to your life, would be controlled by the dam gates, affecting your livelihood, food supply, and navigation.

Your opportunities

Baloria is bound by both its constitution and international agreements, such as Article 19 of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, to consult Indigenous communities on matters that affect them. Since the dam would impact your livelihood, the project cannot proceed without your prior free consent. Legally, it must be ensured that you are adequately consulted and your views on the project are heard. Historically, despite formal legal recognition, there have been numerous abuses of your rights, particularly in complex conflicts where the rights of Indigenous peoples have been indirectly violated through environmental damage. Therefore, you insist more adamantly on your rights and seek to gain the empathy of NGOs and the public. If the dam is built, thousands of the Comnara people would likely be forced to migrate to nearby areas.

Your relationships

You greatly value the support of the NGOs and willingly collaborate with them to achieve your goals. In addition, you are in good contact with local farmers as you have lived together harmoniously in this area for a long time.

However, you have little empathy or understanding for the project's supporters and do not hesitate to stand firm in tough conflicts. Your determination is evident in your unwavering

commitment to your beliefs, and you are prepared to engage in direct resistance if necessary. You also speak openly with the press to clearly communicate your standpoint and experiences in this conflict.

Comnara: Mediator

Who you are

You are a proud member of the Indigenous Comnara community, with a deep connection to your community's heritage and traditions. In the previous government term, you worked in the Ministry of the Environment, a role you found both fulfilling and impactful. However, with the shift to Baloria's liberal party, you had to leave your position. Despite this, your intimate knowledge of political processes drives your continued involvement in advocating for your community. You have taken on the role of mediator to represent and safeguard the interests of the Comnara.

Your community occupies an expansive territory of approximately 2,319,000 hectares. The history of the Comnara is particularly renowned for the intense trade in the 19th century, which significantly shaped your culture and way of life. The Comnara are organised into five distinct regional groups, with one further divided into subgroups. You represent around 10,000 people, united by a rich cultural heritage and a profound connection within the community and to the environment. The traditions and history of the Comnara deeply influence your daily life and your approach to preserving your way of life. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Your goals

As a mediator, your primary objective is to protect the interests of the Comnara people, working in close partnership with the Comnara educator. The proposed dam, although not directly flooding your territory, poses a severe threat to your way of life. The diversion of the river would devastate your fishing practices, groundwater resources, and river transport routes, potentially forcing many Comnara people to relocate against their will. Additionally, the stagnation of water could lead to the spread of waterborne diseases. The environmental impact assessment commissioned by EnergyGrid Alliance, which underpins the dam's approval, is deeply flawed in your view. It neglects to address these crucial concerns, and you are outraged that such a significant environmental disruption is being reduced to mere species loss. Your goal is to ensure that the full environmental impacts are acknowledged from the Comnara perspective and to prevent the dam, and similar projects, from advancing. The river, which is central to your community's livelihood, would be controlled by the dam gates, affecting your food supply, navigation, and overall way of life.

Your opportunities

Baloria is obligated by both its constitution and international agreements, such as Article 19 of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, to consult Indigenous communities on matters that directly affect them. Since the dam project would have a profound impact on your community, it cannot proceed without your prior, informed consent. Legally, it is crucial that your views are adequately considered and respected. Despite the formal recognition of your rights, history shows numerous instances where these rights have been undermined, particularly in conflicts where environmental degradation indirectly violated the rights of Indigenous peoples. Therefore, you are resolute in asserting your rights and seek to garner the support of NGOs and the broader public. If the dam were to be constructed, it could lead

to the displacement of thousands of the Comnara people, a scenario you are determined to prevent.

You are well aware of scenarios where large numbers of Indigenous people were suddenly forced to relocate to larger cities. The resulting hardships—cultural dislocation, loss of traditional livelihoods, and the breakdown of community bonds—are immense. You are determined to prevent your community from enduring such suffering. The prospect of your people being uprooted and thrust into unfamiliar environments, where their identity and way of life would be severely threatened, is something you are resolutely opposed to. Ensuring the preservation of your community's cultural heritage and safeguarding their right to remain on their ancestral lands is of paramount importance to you.

Your relationships

You highly value the support of the NGOs and you are eager to collaborate with them to achieve your goals. You also maintain strong relationships with local farmers, with whom your community has coexisted peacefully for generations. However, you have little sympathy for the dam's proponents and are unafraid to stand firm in the face of conflict. Your commitment to your community is unwavering, and you are prepared to engage in direct resistance if necessary. Additionally, you actively engage with the press to ensure that your community's perspective and experiences are clearly communicated in this conflict.

Newspaper „The Daily Standard“: Journalist

Who you are

As a journalist for the renowned economic newspaper "The Daily Standard," your role is to provide well-informed and balanced reporting, particularly on economic topics. Your focus is on the government's positions and the activities and decisions of involved companies. You adopt a conservative, market-liberal perspective. Personally, you have a vast network of contacts in the business and political scenes and the ability to write persuasive opinion pieces on tight deadlines. Your work helps readers understand complex issues and fosters informed discussion about the project. What you write shapes public opinion and is thus crucial for the negotiations' outcome.

Your task

As a journalist, you do not participate directly in the negotiations. However, you are tasked with continuously posting new content on the online pad to comment on the proceedings. You follow five key areas:

1. **Research and Reporting:** You continuously track developments, political actions, and business activities, creating informative posts based on your research.
2. **Analysis:** You analyse the complex dynamics and trends of the negotiations, informing your readers about their economic and market implications from a market-liberal perspective, also addressing counterarguments.
3. **Interviews:** You conduct interviews with all participants of the dialogue assembly to gain deeper insights into the current debate and understand the various stakeholders' viewpoints, which you then post.
4. **Comments and opinion pieces:** Besides neutral reporting, you write opinion pieces and comments on the economic-political outcomes of the dialogue assembly, defending your conservative and market-liberal stance and advocating for economic freedom and minimal state intervention.
5. **Networking:** You build a network of contacts, especially with NGOs, politicians, and experts, to stay informed about current developments and gain access to relevant information and sources. Ensure no important viewpoints are overlooked.

The media plays a crucial role in economic-political negotiations by bridging different positions and the public. Comprehensive reporting on current developments, political actions, and business activities not only informs the direct participants but also the broader public. This reporting helps create transparency, uncover conflicts of interest, and exert public pressure on political decision-makers and business actors. Moreover, media platforms often provide space for discussions and debates, shedding light on various viewpoints and arguments and promoting the political process. As a journalist, you are thus a mediator and watchdog among the various interest groups. You are expected to relay all significant events but have some leeway in doing so.

For a professional appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may choose business casual attire, complemented by the necessary equipment for high-quality journalism.

While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Note: Twice during the day, there will be Flash News segments where you and your editor-in-chief will have 5 minutes to present the latest updates in a brief live broadcast. Following the final round of negotiations, there will be a longer news broadcast lasting 10 minutes. Begin planning now for the most effective way to present this. In the broadcast, you will have the opportunity to summarise the negotiations and present the outcome to the general public. You can choose your focus and include content from interviews. As the press collective “Unity Dispatch” will also be presenting news broadcasts, please coordinate with them in advance to determine the order of presentation.

Newspaper „The Daily Standard“: Editor-in-Chief

Who you are

As the editor-in-chief of the renowned economic newspaper “The Daily Standard,” your role involves overseeing the editorial direction and ensuring the delivery of well-informed and balanced reporting, particularly on economic topics. You are responsible for shaping the newspaper’s coverage of the government’s positions and the activities and decisions of involved companies, maintaining a conservative, market-liberal perspective. With your extensive network of contacts in the business and political arenas, you guide your team in producing persuasive opinion pieces and comprehensive analyses under tight deadlines. Your work in for the newspaper is vital in shaping public opinion, thereby influencing the outcome of key negotiations.

Your task

As the editor-in-chief of a news outlet, you do not participate directly in the negotiations. However, you are tasked with continuously posting new content on the online pad to comment on the proceedings. You follow five key areas:

1. **Research and Reporting:** You continuously track developments, political actions, and business activities, creating informative posts based on your research.
2. **Analysis:** You analyse the complex dynamics and trends of the negotiations, informing your readers about their economic and market implications from a market-liberal perspective, also addressing counterarguments.
3. **Interviews:** You conduct interviews with all participants of the dialogue assembly to gain deeper insights into the current debate and understand the various stakeholders’ viewpoints, which you then post.
4. **Comments and opinion pieces:** Besides neutral reporting, you write opinion pieces and comments on the economic-political outcomes of the dialogue assembly, defending your conservative and market-liberal stance and advocating for economic freedom and minimal state intervention.
5. **Networking:** You build a network of contacts, especially with NGOs, politicians, and experts, to stay informed about current developments and gain access to relevant information and sources. Ensure no important viewpoints are overlooked.

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For a professional appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may choose business casual attire, complemented by the necessary equipment for high-quality journalism. While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Note: Twice during the day, there will be Flash News segments where you and your journalist teammate will have 5 minutes to present the latest updates in a brief live broadcast. Following the final round of negotiations, there will be a longer news broadcast lasting 10 minutes. Begin planning now for the most effective way to present this. In the broadcast, you will have the opportunity to summarise the negotiations and present the outcome to the general public. You can choose your focus and include content from interviews. As the press collective “Unity Dispatch” will also be presenting news broadcasts, please coordinate with them in advance to determine the order of presentation.

Press Collective „Unity Dispatch“: Journalist

Who you are

As a journalist for the progressive press collective "Unity Dispatch" for online media, your role is to provide well-informed and balanced reporting. You are known for focusing on the voices and concerns of marginalized groups and advocating for environmental issues. Your reporting is characterised by a critical perspective on political and economic decisions, ensuring that counterpoints are also highlighted. You have an extensive network among social and environmental activists and in the political scene, allowing you to incorporate diverse perspectives and present complex topics clearly. Your work primarily speaks to a young audience, informing them about important social issues and encouraging them to think critically. You are a key figure in the modern media landscape, playing an important role in driving the discourse on relevant topics and fostering change. Your reporting has often sparked significant protest movements, which you view as a particular success, shaping public opinion.

Your task

As a journalist, you do not participate directly in the negotiations. However, you are tasked with continuously posting new content on the online pad to comment on the proceedings. You follow five key areas:

1. **Research and Reporting:** You continuously track developments, political actions, and business activities, creating informative posts based on your research.
2. **Analysis:** You analyse the complex dynamics and trends of the negotiations, informing your readers about their impact on the population, focusing on the perspectives of marginalized groups and considering the arguments' environmental and social justice implications. You also address counterarguments.
3. **Interviews:** You conduct interviews with all participants of the dialogue assembly to gain deeper insights into the current debate and understand the various stakeholders' viewpoints, which you then post.
4. **Comments and opinion pieces:** Besides neutral reporting, you write opinion pieces and comments on the political outcomes of the dialogue assembly, giving marginalized groups a voice in the public sphere and advocating for greater social justice and environmental protection.
5. **Networking:** You build a network of contacts, especially with NGOs, politicians, and experts, to stay informed about current developments and gain access to relevant information and sources. Ensure no important viewpoints are overlooked.

The media plays a crucial role in economic-political negotiations by bridging different positions and the public. Comprehensive reporting on current developments, political actions, and business activities not only informs the direct participants but also the broader public. This reporting helps create transparency, uncover conflicts of interest, and exert public pressure on political decision-makers and business actors. Moreover, media platforms often provide space for discussions and debates, shedding light on various viewpoints and arguments and promoting the political process. As a journalist, you are thus a mediator and watchdog among

the various interest groups. You are expected to relay all significant events but have some leeway in doing so.

For a professional appearance during the Terra Dourada Dialogue Assembly, you may choose business casual attire, complemented by the necessary equipment for high-quality journalism. While optional, this attire can enhance your presence and confidence. Remember to approach the assembly with respect for both the individuals you represent and those with whom you are negotiating.

Note: Twice during the day, there will be Flash News segments where you and your online editor will have 5 minutes to present the latest updates in a brief live broadcast. Following the final round of negotiations, there will be a longer news broadcast lasting 10 minutes. Begin planning now for the most effective way to present this. In the broadcast, you will have the opportunity to summarise the negotiations and present the outcome to the general public. You can choose your focus and include content from interviews. As the press collective “The Daily Standard” will also be presenting news broadcasts, please coordinate with them in advance to determine the order of presentation.

Press Collective „Unity Dispatch“: Online Editor

As an online editor for the progressive press collective “Unity Dispatch”, your role involves curating and overseeing the publication of well-informed and balanced content. You focus on amplifying the voices and concerns of marginalized groups while advocating for environmental issues, ensuring that critical perspectives on political and economic decisions are well-represented. With your extensive network among social and environmental activists and in the political sphere, you integrate diverse viewpoints to present complex topics clearly and engagingly. “Unity Dispatch” targets a young audience, aiming to inform them about pressing social issues and encourage critical thinking. As a key figure in the digital media landscape, it drives the discourse on important topics and contribute to fostering change, with your content often sparking significant protest movements and shaping public opinion.

Your task

As the online editor of a news outlet, you do not participate directly in the negotiations. However, you are tasked with continuously posting new content on the online pad to comment on the proceedings. You follow five key areas:

1. **Research and Reporting:** You continuously track developments, political actions, and business activities, creating informative posts based on your research.
2. **Analysis:** You analyse the complex dynamics and trends of the negotiations, informing your readers about their impact on the population, focusing on the perspectives of marginalized groups and considering the arguments' environmental and social justice implications. You also address counterarguments.
3. **Interviews:** You conduct interviews with all participants of the dialogue assembly to gain deeper insights into the current debate and understand the various stakeholders' viewpoints, which you then post.
4. **Comments and opinion pieces:** Besides neutral reporting, you write opinion pieces and comments on the political outcomes of the dialogue assembly, giving marginalized groups a voice in the public sphere and advocating for greater social justice and environmental protection.
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Note: Twice during the day, there will be Flash News segments where you and your journalist teammate will have 5 minutes to present the latest updates in a brief live broadcast. Following the final round of negotiations, there will be a longer news broadcast lasting 10 minutes. Begin planning now for the most effective way to present this. In the broadcast, you will have the opportunity to summarise the negotiations and present the outcome to the general public. You can choose your focus and include content from interviews. As the press collective “The Daily Standard” will also be presenting news broadcasts, please coordinate with them in advance to determine the order of presentation.

Event Cards

Hunger Strike among the Comnara

News for the Press: Liora, a 25-year-old member of the Indigenous Comnara community, has begun a hunger strike in a nearby town to the proposed hydroelectric plant. By completely abstaining from food, she aims to highlight what the construction of the dam would mean for her community: the destruction of their livelihood. She intends to continue her strike until the fundamental rights of her community are acknowledged and respected. Other Comnara members plan to join the hunger strike if the negotiations do not favour environmental preservation. The press can decide creatively how to break this news (e.g., distributing a picture of Liora on strike).

Secret deal with Volt uncovered

News for the Press: The website Indimedia has leaked secret agreements between the CEO of Volt, the President and the President's First Secretary of Baloria. According to these agreements, the President has promised the electric car company Volt two years of tax-free exports following the successful establishment of a Gigafactory in Baloria. These agreements are not compliant with the Balorian constitution. In the latest poll, the ruling party's share of voters has dropped by 11 percentage points. The President is now under criticism for corruption allegations. The press can decide creatively how to break this news (e.g., distributing pictures of the President and Volt CEO making a deal).

Influencer takes a stand

News for the Press: The globally renowned actress and influencer Amara Leander has spoken out about the conflict on various social media platforms. She wrote: "If we stop this hydroelectric plant, we stop Baloria. Who dares to place their own needs above the future of the country?" Her posts have been shared thousands of times and continue to receive significant support from the public. The positions between the dam's supporters and opponents are hardening.

Catholic Church's Letter to the Ministry of the Environment

News for the Press: Bishop Paulo Martinez, head of the Balorian Committee for Social Justice of the Catholic Church, has written an official letter to the Balorian Ministry of the Environment in which he outlines the environmental risks and human rights violations of the project, positioning himself strictly against the planned construction. As a result, the Ministry of the Environment is invited by the Press to publicly respond to the Bishop's concerns.

Instruction for the Negotiation Facilitator: Ask the Ministry of the Environment to stand up and speak publicly in front of the Press and the Assembly. Members of the Press are invited to ask provocative interview questions to the Ministry (maximum 3 minutes in total).

Corruption allegation

Instruction for the Negotiation Facilitator: The person who has spoken the most so far is taken into custody due to a corruption allegation and must remain silent for 15 minutes, outside the room. The negotiation facilitator will identify the person with the highest speaking time and

inform the press about their detention for corruption charges. The press will inform all participants. After 15 minutes, the negotiation facilitator will inform the press that the corruption allegation has been dropped. The person will be released and may actively participate in the negotiations again.

Protest

News for the Press: A large crowd has gathered outside the doors of the dialogue assembly. Following reports from “Change Times” and calls from the national NGO “Sustainability Network Baloria,” around 50,000 peaceful demonstrators are now taking a clear stand against the construction of the dam. Only a few hours earlier, there was an arson attack on construction equipment belonging to a subsidiary of EnergyGrid Solutions, which is contracted to build the roads to the dam. The perpetrators of the arson attack remain unknown. There were no injuries.

Instruction for the Negotiation Facilitator: Consider hanging protest signs when the press will be announcing this news.

Study on energy reduction

News for the Press: An independent study by the Institute of Energy Innovation and Utilization shows that Baloria could reduce its expected electricity demand by 40% within four years by investing in energy efficiency. The saved energy would be equivalent to the output of 14 comparable hydroelectric plants and could lead to national electricity savings of up to 19 billion USD.

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AGRIMAX

- INNOVATIONS -

Photo by Scott Goodwill

Leading Agriculture in Baloria

- Founded in 2014, specializing in large-scale farming with crops like soybeans, maize, sugarcane and cotton.
- Cutting-edge technology for sustainable, high-yield farming.
- Operations span across Baloria with headquarters in the Global North.

31 irrigation systems

580 000 hectares land

Unlocking Agricultural Potential

- Stable water supply ensures crop yields, even during droughts, and increases production capacity.
- Hydropower provides sustainable energy for processing facilities.

AGRIMAX
- INNOVATIONS -

Creating Value for All

For Communities:

Job creation and improved infrastructure.

For the Environment:

Precision farming to minimize waste and maximize efficiency. Reforestation projects and biodiversity conservation efforts.

For Baloria:

Expanded production and tax revenue.

Photo by Simona Sergi

AGRIMAX
- INNOVATIONS -

*Thank you for
your support.*

Photo by Spencer Scott Pugh

Volt

Driving Change, Together.

Who We Are:

Volt is a global leader in high-end electric vehicles, driven by innovation, sustainability, and cutting-edge technology.

Our Vision:

To make electric mobility accessible and sustainable for all, while maintaining premium quality and performance.

The Gigafactory in Maravilha do Norte

Strategic Location:

- Political stability, excellent maritime connections, and reduced production costs.
- Renewable energy reliance to maintain sustainability.

Factory Goals:

- Achieve an annual production target of 2 million cars.
- Lower unit production costs to make Volt EVs affordable and accessible globally.

Photo by Erik Knoef on Unsplash

Building Tomorrow Together

- ✓ Creating thousands of jobs locally.
- ✓ Contributing to Baloria's GDP with large-scale exports and attracting key suppliers.
- ✓ Sustainable production without compromise.

Sustainability Through Renewable Energy

Energy Needs:

- The Gigafactory will require **200 MW** of renewable energy.
- Hydropower is essential for Volt's green manufacturing process.

Infrastructure Needs:

- Reliable railways, water access, and roads are critical for success.

Photo by Art Lasovskyon on Unsplash

ENERGY GRID

Our mission is to deliver *innovative, sustainable, and efficient* energy solutions that balance economic growth with environmental responsibility.

ENERGY GRID

Hydropower: Clean Energy, Bright Future

- Powers 2 million homes and Volt's Gigafactory with clean energy.
- Impact assessments show minimal biodiversity loss.
- Commits to reforestation, social projects, and wildlife conservation.

Energy Production (MW)

Legend:

- Hydroelectric power station
- reservoir
- Volt Gigafactory

A Project of National Significance

4 000

jobs during construction

200

permanent roles post-completion

\$19.5 billion

estimated contribution to GDP over 5 years

The Road Ahead

ENERGY GRID

Thank you!

ECOVISION GLOBAL

WHO WE ARE

International NGO dedicated to environmental protection and sustainable development.

- **Scope:** Operating in 50+ countries, partnering with local NGOs.
- **Funding:** 100% donation-based for independence.
- **Values:** Environmental integrity, social equity, and transparency.

OUR GOALS

1. **Protect Ecosystems:** Halt destructive projects like the Baloria dam.
2. **Promote Renewable Energy:** Advocate for solar, wind, and community-driven solutions.
3. **Empower Communities:** Ensure local participation and fight corruption.
4. **Uphold Rights:** Enforce environmental and human rights agreements.

WHY IT MATTERS

1. **Ecosystems at Risk:** Tropical forests and biodiversity face destruction.
2. **Social Justice:** Projects funnel profits to wealthy nations, harming locals.
3. **The Reality About Dams:** Emit greenhouse gases and are inefficient due to climate shifts.

TAKE ACTION

Support us & Join the movement!

Donate, raise awareness, and demand accountability. Together, we can protect our planet and communities.

ECOVISION GLOBAL